

The Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases
Research Infrastructure

Community Handbook 2025

ACTRIS Collaborative
Network

ACTRIS

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Research Infrastructure

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A word of introduction

ACTRIS has always been more than a research infrastructure — it is a community of nations, institutions, and individuals united by a shared commitment to advancing atmospheric science and providing impactful services to society.

This handbook offers insights into the key components of the ACTRIS community. It highlights the ACTRIS ERIC countries, whose political support and contributions form the foundation of our operations. It also acknowledges the dedication of countries currently striving to join our community, such as Portugal, Greece, Estonia, and Ireland. Their efforts demonstrate the continued appeal and relevance of ACTRIS as a cornerstone of atmospheric research in Europe and beyond.

We are also proud to collaborate with external partners such as the Joint Research Centre, whose engagement strengthens our capacity to deliver scientific excellence and innovative solutions to global challenges.

The ACTRIS Community Handbook clearly expresses the power of partnership and represents a resource for everyone connected to ACTRIS, from researchers and policymakers to educators and innovators. Together, we are building an open, inclusive, and dynamic community that is equipped to meet the challenges of the future.

Thank you for being part of this community.

Eija Juurola

ACTRIS ERIC Director General

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1. Introduction

The ACTRIS Community Handbook highlights the essential components of the ACTRIS community that contribute to the success of the Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure (ACTRIS). By showcasing the national facilities, research organizations, and funding mechanisms that support ACTRIS, this document provides a comprehensive overview of the collaborative efforts driving advancements in atmospheric sciences.

About ACTRIS

ACTRIS is a distributed research infrastructure providing access to high-quality and long-term data, methodologies and services about the 4D variability and the physical, optical and chemical properties of short-lived atmospheric constituents.

The mission of ACTRIS is to improve the current capacity to analyse, understand, and predict past, current, and future evolution of the atmospheric environment. ACTRIS data and services enable a wide range of applications, from improving climate and air quality models, such as those from the Copernicus program, to validating satellite observations, for instance, the ESA and Jaxa's Mission EarthCare. ACTRIS' scientific components also support collaborations with global research networks and organizations, making ACTRIS a cornerstone of international atmospheric research.

ACTRIS is organized with four main elements:

- ACTRIS National Facilities consist of advanced Observational and Exploratory Platforms, such as ground-based stations, mobile platforms, and atmospheric simulation chambers. These platforms generate in situ and remote-sensing data on aerosol, clouds, and reactive trace gases, contributing to our understanding of their roles in atmospheric processes, air quality, ecosystem interactions, and climate.
- ACTRIS Topical Centres are responsible for developing and maintaining high-quality measurement protocols, ensuring calibration and standardization, and providing technical and scientific expertise. These facilities play a pivotal role in harmonizing observational methods across the network, fostering consistency and reliability in data collection.
- ACTRIS Data Centre manages data collection, curation, and dissemination according to the ACTRIS Data Policy and FAIR principles.
- ACTRIS Head Office coordinates the operational work of the whole research infrastructure at the European level.

ACTRIS is the result of more than 14 years of continuous development, supported by both ACTRIS Countries and the European Commission through the Research Infrastructure programmes. Over this period, ACTRIS has grown into a world-class research infrastructure with a total investment of approximately €698 million, supporting its design, implementation, and operational phases (Fig.1).

The initiative began in 2011 as an Integrated Infrastructure project, building on four major European research collaborations:

- EARLINET (European Aerosol Research Lidar Network, EU-FP5 and FP6 projects),
- EUSAAR (European Supersites for Atmospheric Aerosol Research, EU-FP6 project),
- CREATE (Construction, use, and delivery of a European aerosol database, EU-FP5 project),
- Cloudnet originated as an EU-FP5 project for observing cloud profiles.

Over time, ACTRIS expanded to integrate long-term trace gas observation networks.

The initiative advanced further during its design phase funded through the H2020 programme (2014–2015). In 2016, ACTRIS was recognized as a project on the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) Roadmap, marking its scientific and strategic maturity and setting the stage for its full implementation within the next decade.

Figure 1. The timeline chart illustrates the key phases and investments of ACTRIS from 2014 to 2038. It highlights the Design Phase (2014–2016, 86 M€), Preparation Phase (2017–2019, 93 M€), Implementation Phase (2020–2023, 520 M€) summed up to a Total Investment (2014-2023) of 699M€. The ongoing Operation Phase started in 2024 with an annual cost of 95 M€. Key milestones include ACTRIS becoming an ESFRI Project in 2016, achieving ESFRI Landmark status in 2021, and establishing ACTRIS ERIC in 2023.

The Preparatory Phase of ACTRIS required an investment of approximately €93 million, partially funded by the European Commission, to establish the legal, governance, financial, technical, and strategic foundations of the research infrastructure.

The Implementation Phase began in 2020 with an investment of €520 million, supported in part by the ACTRIS Implementation Project (ACTRIS IMP). This phase focused on developing the necessary structures to support national and European-level implementation efforts. In 2021, ACTRIS was designated as an ESFRI Landmark research infrastructure, a recognition of its long-term impact and strategic importance for European science and innovation.

Two years later, in 2023, ACTRIS was officially established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), signifying its transition from a project-based network to a sustainable, legally recognized research infrastructure. The establishment of ACTRIS ERIC reinforces the role of atmospheric research in advancing scientific knowledge and delivering societal benefits. Member and observer countries commit to supporting ACTRIS over the next five years, ensuring scientific excellence across Europe. Membership in ACTRIS ERIC allows countries to actively shape the strategic direction of the research infrastructure, fostering collaboration in aerosol, clouds, and trace gas research. Furthermore, ACTRIS ERIC strengthens national consortia and facilities by ensuring operational support, enhancing their role within the broader research ecosystem.

As of 2025, ACTRIS is in its operational phase. While many services are already accessible, the infrastructure is expected to reach full operational capacity by 2026. The estimated annual core budget for this phase is approximately €95 million, with:

- €77 million allocated to National Facilities in ACTRIS ERIC Countries,
- €16.5 million supporting ACTRIS Topical Centres and the Data Centre, operated by over 30 research-performing organizations,
- €1.5 million dedicated to ACTRIS ERIC operations.

ACTRIS Collaborative Framework for Operations and Strategy

The ACTRIS Collaborative Framework brings together countries committed to advancing atmospheric research through ACTRIS. The map below (Fig.2) illustrates the current ACTRIS ERIC Countries, as well as other countries (ACTRIS-Engaging Countries) actively engaging with ACTRIS and working towards joining ACTRIS ERIC in the future.

Countries join ACTRIS ERIC as members, permanent observers, and observers through ministry-level commitments. While the commitment is long-term, members or permanent observers may withdraw after five years of ACTRIS ERIC's establishment by submitting an official request, as outlined in the [ACTRIS ERIC Statutes](#).

Member countries pay annual membership contributions, which are used to support the annual operations of the ACTRIS Central Facilities and ACTRIS National Facilities. Countries and institutions hosting ACTRIS Central Facility Units commit to fully supporting their implementation and covering approximately 70% of their operational costs.

Figure 2. The map shows ACTRIS ERIC Countries and ACTRIS-Engaging Countries. Detailed information on each country is provided in the following sections of the ACTRIS Community Handbook.

ACTRIS operates through a well-defined governance and organizational structure designed to ensure effective coordination, decision-making, and long-term sustainability. Figure 3 outlines the key bodies, their roles, and the mechanisms that guide the strategic and operational management of ACTRIS.

The ACTRIS General Assembly, composed of delegates from member and observer countries, serves as the highest decision-making body in ACTRIS, supported by the Scientific and Innovation Advisory Board and the Ethical Advisory Board. ACTRIS ERIC, as the statutory seat of the research infrastructure, is responsible for implementing the General Assembly's decisions. Led by the Director General, it oversees the coordination and operation at the European level of the distributed research infrastructure and its Central Facilities.

Key internal advisory bodies include the Research Infrastructure Committee, the National Facilities Scientific and Technical Forum, and the Atmospheric Simulation Chamber Committee, ensuring active community engagement in the strategic and scientific development of ACTRIS. At the national level, ACTRIS activities are coordinated by the ACTRIS National Consortia, with the National Contact Person acting as a crucial link between the national and European levels, as well as the ACTRIS ERIC.

The operations of ACTRIS ERIC and the Central Facilities are evaluated regularly, to ascertain that the activities are continuously aligned with the vision and mission of ACTRIS, and the long-term strategy. The results of the evaluation support the General Assembly in the development of ACTRIS.

Figure 3. Key bodies, their roles, and the mechanisms that guide the strategic and operational management of ACTRIS. The RI committee, the National Facilities (NF) Scientific and Technical Forum and the Atmospheric Simulation Chamber Committee ensure that the scientific and strategic development of ACTRIS aligns with user and stakeholder expectations. The Scientific and Innovation Advisory Board and the Ethical Advisory Board are providing advice to the General Assembly. Red arrows indicate a relationship involving financial flow among components, while grey arrows describe the relationship between the different parts of ACTRIS without financial flow.

ACTRIS Financial Process

ACTRIS ERIC Head Office is responsible for collecting annual membership contributions from the ACTRIS ERIC Countries (members, permanent observers, and observers) to support the operations of the Central Facilities. The Head Office distributes the collected annual membership contributions to the organisations hosting the Central Facility Units based on the decision of the General Assembly. National Facilities are funded through national contributions only.

According to the ACTRIS ERIC Internal Financial rules, the approval of the annual budget by the General Assembly constitutes the obligation of each ACTRIS ERIC Country (member, permanent observer, and observer) to pay its annual membership contribution to ACTRIS ERIC as defined in the budget.

The 5-year ACTRIS Financial Plan, approved by the General Assembly, establishes the general framework for the detailed annual budget of ACTRIS, based on the work plans and related financial plans provided by each Central Facility for the upcoming 5 years. The annual budget is approved yearly by the General Assembly and it includes:

- a) revenues and expenditures for the financial year to which they relate,
- b) information on the balance of the budget,
- c) the associated work plan describing the objectives and activities, and justifying the planned revenues and expenditures.

The revenues consist of host (premium) contributions, membership contributions and any other income. Host contribution means in-cash or in-kind contribution that the host organisation of a Central Facility Unit is providing to its Unit. Host contribution is agreed to be approximately 70% of the Central Facility Unit costs and it shall not account for less than 50% of an annual budget. The annual membership contribution collected from the countries supports the Central Facilities' operations, and it should be approximately 30% of the revenues. If there are additional costs, other revenues can be used to balance the income.

ACTRIS Impacts

ACTRIS fosters long-term and short-term observations of aerosols, clouds, and trace gases, which are critical for assessing air pollution trends, understanding climate feedback mechanisms, and improving numerical models. By maintaining standardized measurement protocols and state-of-the-art calibration techniques, ACTRIS ensures that data collected across its network are intercomparable and reliable. This allows researchers and any other users to track changes in atmospheric composition over time and assess the impact of human activities and natural events, such as wildfires or volcanic eruptions, on air quality and climate. ACTRIS data are used to validate satellite observations, improving the accuracy of remote sensing technologies and ensuring consistency between ground-based and spaceborne measurements. This synergy is crucial for advancing Earth system models and climate simulations, which are essential for informed decision-making and sustainable development policies.

ACTRIS continuously develops and tests new measurement techniques, advancing the capabilities of atmospheric research. It also fosters collaboration with the private sector, supporting the development of cutting-edge environmental technologies and services. Through its training programmes and access opportunities, ACTRIS provides researchers and industry stakeholders with hands-on experience in state-of-the-art atmospheric measurement techniques. These initiatives help bridge the gap between research and innovation, ensuring that scientific knowledge translates into practical solutions for environmental challenges. ACTRIS embraces open science principles, offering free and open access to its data, measurement facilities, and expertise. This commitment to transparency and collaboration enables a wide range of users to leverage ACTRIS resources for scientific research, policy development, and technological innovation. As climate change and air pollution continue to pose significant global threats, ACTRIS remains committed to providing high-quality atmospheric data and services that support evidence-based decision-making. By fostering international cooperation and advancing atmospheric science, ACTRIS contributes to building a more sustainable and resilient future for all.

The Value of National and Organizational Contributions to ACTRIS

The strength of ACTRIS is rooted in its collaborative network, where the contributions of ACTRIS ERIC Countries, External Partners, such as JRC officially contributing to ACTRIS with one National Facility, and ACTRIS-Engaging Countries amplify the collective impact. The facilities, expertise and long-term commitment provided by these contributors ensure comprehensive and high-quality observational data and services, enabling advancements in understanding atmospheric processes, climate modelling, air quality management, and satellite calibration. This collaboration embodies the vision of ACTRIS as a hub for innovation, education, and scientific excellence.

Acknowledgement of Key Stakeholders

We extend our gratitude to the national governments, research institutions, and funding agencies, whose support and dedication make ACTRIS possible. Their continued investment in ACTRIS strengthens its capacity to address scientific and societal challenges on a global scale.

These sections are organized into country and organizational profiles, each detailing the contributions of ACTRIS ERIC Countries, external partners, and Countries engaging with ACTRIS.

The profiles are arranged alphabetically for easy reference and are intended to provide an accessible yet detailed overview of each entity's unique contributions.

Each profile includes key information about:

- ACTRIS National Contact Person
- Delegates of the ACTRIS General Assembly
- Research Performing Organizations (RPOs): Institutions and teams contributing to ACTRIS' scientific and operational goals.
- National and Central Facilities (NF and CF).

For ACTRIS National Facilities, information will be provided on both existing and planned observational components.

ACTRIS includes six observational components:

- Aerosol In Situ (Aerosol IS)
- Aerosol Remote Sensing (Aerosol RS)
- Cloud In Situ (Cloud IS)
- Cloud Remote Sensing (Cloud RS)
- Reactive Trace Gases In Situ (RTG IS)
- Reactive Trace Gases Remote Sensing (RTG RS)

To ensure up-to-date information, all National Facilities' labels in the tables have been replaced with placeholders marked "X." The "X" indicates the readiness level of each observational component:

- Initially Accepted
- Ready for Labelling (minor upgrades required)
- Planned with Major Upgrades

ACTRIS-Austria

National Contact Person:

Jochen Wagner

Division for Biomedical Physics
Medical University of Innsbruck

Membership status in the ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly:

Member

Nominated delegate:

- Karolina Begusch-Pfefferkorn

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS:

- Austrian Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research
- FWF Austrian Science Fund
- The Austrian Research Promotion Agency

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium:

- Institute of Atmospheric and Cryospheric Sciences (ACINN), University of Innsbruck
- Sonnblick Observatory, Geosphere Austria
- Aerosol Physics & Environmental Physics (AEP), Universität Wien
- Division of Biomedical Physics, Medical University Innsbruck
- Institut for Meteorology (Boku-Met), University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna
- LuftBlick Earth Observatory Technologies, Innsbruck
- Vienna University of Technology (TU), Research Group for Environmental Analytics
- TU Graz, Institute of Electrical Measurement and Sensor Systems

Highlights

Spanning a diverse range of atmospheric research, the following highlights showcase significant advancements in understanding and addressing critical environmental challenges, including nitrogen oxide dynamics, urban air quality, cloud detection, aerosol measurements, vehicle emissions monitoring, and emerging issues such as microplastics and Arctic aerosols.

Nitrogen Oxides (NOx) Dynamics: Investigations into the external cycling of nitrogen oxides (NOx) under various atmospheric conditions have enhanced the understanding of NOx dynamics, a crucial factor in air quality and atmospheric chemistry.

Urban Air Quality: Analysis of the impact of elevated NOx levels in urban environments on ozone fluxes has provided valuable insights into the interplay between urban emissions and air quality.

Cloud Detection and Classification: The development of an innovative algorithm for automatic cloud detection and classification using airborne in situ observations has improved cloud characterization and the understanding of their role in climate and weather systems.

Aerosol Measurement Advancements: Characterization of the aerosol inlet and transport system during the A-LIFE aircraft field experiment has advanced techniques for accurately measuring aerosols, critical for understanding their impact on climate and air quality.

Microplastics in the Atmosphere: Analyses of micro- and nanoplastic concentrations in fine particulate matter samples from the high alpine station Sonnblick in Austria have addressed emerging environmental concerns related to plastic pollution in the atmosphere.

Arctic Aerosol Sources: Investigations into the composition and sources of carbonaceous aerosols at the Zeppelin Observatory in Svalbard have enhanced the understanding of Arctic aerosol sources and their influence on regional and global climate.

Urban Atmospheric Chemistry: Temporal analysis of nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and ozone (O₃) in Rome using Pandora instruments and in situ measurements has contributed to a better understanding of urban atmospheric chemistry and its implications for air quality management.

Vehicle Emission Monitoring: Qualitative and quantitative analyses of car exhaust plumes using a gas Schlieren imaging sensor system have advanced methodologies for remote monitoring of vehicle emissions, supporting efforts to reduce transport-related pollution.

Contribution to the ACTRIS Central Facilities

Central Facility (CF)	CF Unit name	CF Unit description	CF Unit hosting institution
Centre for Reactive Trace Gases Remote Sensing (CREGARS)	UVVIS AT	Facilitating the generation of highest-standard reference data of several key trace gases using ground-based remote sensing techniques.	Innsbruck Medical University
Centre for Cloud In Situ Measurements (CIS)	ECCINT	<p>The European Centre for cloud ambient intercomparison (ECCINT) is responsible for the mandatory integrated cloud probes such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> cloud liquid water content cloud droplet effective radius <p>The liquid water content is important in figuring out which types of clouds are likely to form and is strongly linked to three other cloud microphysical variables: the cloud droplet effective radius, the cloud drop number concentration, and the cloud drop size distribution.</p> <p>ECCINT will support cloud in situ National Facilities across Europe to provide high-quality data sets to ACTRIS.</p>	GeoSphere Austria

ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
Sonnblick Observatory (SBO)	Observational Platform	47.054°N 12.958°E 3106 m a.s.l.	X	X				

University Innsbruck (UIBK)	Observational Platform	47.264°N 11.383°E 616 m a.s.l.			X			
University Vienna (UNIVIE)	Observational Platform	48.221°N 16.356°E 185 m a.s.l.	X					

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

The ACTRIS-AT Consortium is well-established. Each member has signed an MoU and anchored ACTRIS administratively at the management level.

There is an annual ACTRIS AT meeting. Recently (2024) a new member (TU Graz) joined the consortium.

 <https://actris.i-med.ac.at/>

Funding for ACTRIS

ACTRIS was established at the administrative level of the national Research Performing Organisations. Furthermore, the Austrian Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research pays the annual membership contribution. There are several ongoing research projects related to ACTRIS and funded by FWF, ESA, NASA, etc.

Users of ACTRIS

- The eight partners in Austria are important users of ACTRIS
- Other Research Performing Organisations in Austria, especially in the framework of nationally-funded research projects (FFG, FWF)
- Environmental Agency Austria (collaboration for the new Air quality directive)
- ESA (European Space Agency) / NASA (National Aeronautics and Space Administration) for ground-based validation of reactive trace gas retrievals
- Collaboration with the private sector is very strong: the private company LuftBlick is a member of the national consortium, and many instrument developers cooperate with Sonnblick Observatory
- Sonnblick is already a member of GAW (Global Atmosphere Watch) with users via WMO (World Meteorological Organisation)
- Geosphere Austria (the national weather service) will use ACTRIS data for model data assimilation, development and validation

ACTRIS-Belgium

National Contact Person:

Bart Dils

Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy (BIRA-IASB)

Membership status in the ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly:

Member

Nominated delegate:

- Aline van der Werf

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS:

- Federal Belgian Science Policy

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium:

- Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy (BIRA-IASB)
- Royal Meteorological Institute of Belgium (KMI-IRM)
- University of Liège (ULiège)
- Institut Scientifique de Service Public (ISSEP)

MEMBER

Highlights

Belgian Research Performing Organisations contribute to ACTRIS in various ways. As part of the CREGARS Central Facility, they support reactive trace gas remote sensing measurements within ACTRIS. As operators of National Facilities, they deliver high-quality data, and as operators of mobile platforms, they provide researchers the opportunity to set up campaigns.

Within CREGARS, the Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy (BIRA-IASB) provides the overall lead as well as the leads of the clusters dealing with the Fourier-transform infrared spectrometers (FTIR) and ultraviolet-visible (UV-VIS) spectrometers. In this role, significant efforts have been made to formalize the relationship between ACTRIS and the NDACC (Network for the Detection of Atmospheric Composition Change) and PGN (Pandonia Global Network) research networks, ensuring that retrieval and instrumentation requirements remain aligned. ACTRIS-type measurements, which are processed through a centralized data processing and QA/QC system at BIRA-IASB, are designed to meet NDACC and PGN requirements and are also accessible via the NDACC and PGN data portals whenever appropriate. These principles were formalized in corresponding Memoranda of Understanding.

BIRA-IASB also plays a leading role in the development and testing of more compact FTIR systems. Instruments such as the Bruker EM27-Sun have already proven highly valuable to the satellite validation community. However, their spectral range in the near-infrared allows retrieval of only some key greenhouse gas species, making them complementary to the TCCON (Total Carbon Column Observing Network) network only. A similarly compact instrument that operates in the mid-infrared would be an ideal complement to NDACC/ACTRIS, opening the possibility of mobile ACTRIS FTIR platforms. For National Facility candidates, such an instrument combined with other trace gas remote sensing tools could provide a more budget-friendly alternative to the currently required high-resolution FTIR systems. To this end, several test campaigns and productive discussions with industrial partners are ongoing.

In 2024, the quadrennial UV-VIS instrument inter-comparison campaign, organized by the Dutch partners within CREGARS, saw significant contributions from BIRA-IASB. This event also provided an ideal platform to test our UV-VIS mobile reference instrument, a key component of our quality monitoring obligations within CREGARS.

Both the Reactive Trace Gas Remote Sensing National Facilities at Réunion Island (a French/Belgian site) and the Aerosol in situ National Facility at Vielsalm have passed the first phase of the labelling process. Other sites have also made notable progress in acquiring instruments that meet ACTRIS requirements. For example, the Belgian candidate Reactive Trace Gas Remote Sensing National Facility at the Jungfraujoch station, located in the Swiss Alps, replaced its old FTIR instrument with a state-of-the-art Bruker Vertex 80v FTIR instrument. To ensure consistency between the old and new instruments—crucial for long-term trend analysis—and to bridge the time gap, a compact Bruker Invenio FTIR instrument, provided by our German partners within CREGARS, conducted parallel measurements for several months. These measurements also provide valuable test data for ongoing low-resolution FTIR development work.

Contribution to the ACTRIS Central Facilities

Central Facility (CF)	CF Unit name	CF Unit description	CF Unit hosting institution
Centre for Reactive Trace Gases Remote Sensing (CREGARS)	CREGARS-FTIR-BE	<p><u>CREGARS-FTIR-BE BIRA:</u> CREGARS lead. CREGARS FTIR cluster lead. Management and coordination of the consortium and FTIR cluster. Development of FTIR retrieval strategies. Provision of guidelines and procedures. Interaction with the NDACC community. Operation of the FTIR central processing and QA/QC system. Provision of services to National Facilities and users operating FTIR instruments for atmospheric observations of ACTRIS target trace gases.</p> <p><u>CREGARS-FTIR-BE ULiege:</u> Development of FTIR retrieval strategies. Provision of guidelines and procedures. Interaction with the NDACC community.</p>	Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy, University of Liège
Centre for Reactive Trace Gases Remote Sensing (CREGARS)	CREGARS-UVVIS-BE	<p>CREGARS UV-VIS cluster lead. Management and coordination of the UV-VIS cluster. Development of retrieval strategies, and provision of guidelines and procedures for MAX-DOAS type UV-VIS instruments. Interaction with the NDACC community. Operation of the UV-VIS MAX-DOAS central processing and QA/QC system. Provision of services to National Facilities and users operating UV-VIS instruments for atmospheric observations of ACTRIS target trace gases.</p>	Royal Belgian Institute for Space Aeronomy

ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
MARTISLAB-BE	Mobile Platform	Mobile			X			
Observatoire de Physique de l'Atmosphère à La Réunion (OPAR) (Franco-Belgian National Facility)	Observational Platform	21.1°S 55.4°E 2200 m a.s.l.						X
Scientific Station of the Jungfraujoch	Observational Platform	46.55°N 7.89°E 3572 m a.s.l.						X
Ukkel	Observational Platform	50.78°N 4.35°E 105 m a.s.l.	X					
Vielsalm	Observational Platform	50.27°N 5.9°E 494 m a.s.l.	X		X			

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

The ACTRIS-Belgium consortium and roadmap have essentially remained the same since the start of ACTRIS PPP. One additional partner (VITO) is seeking affiliation with ACTRIS-Belgium: VITO or Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek has proposed the addition of a mobile combined aerosol and trace gas in situ facility as well as a compact mobile aerosol platform. The proposal has been discussed within the ACTRIS Belgium consortium, as well as with CiGAS and CAIS-ECAC, and has been submitted for funding to the Flemish FWO (Fonds voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek) funding agency.

Funding for ACTRIS

ACTRIS-Belgium is coordinated by BIRA-IASB and supported for three more years starting March 15th 2024 by the Federal Belgian Science Policy and host institutions. The latter provides the Belgian delegate to the ACTRIS General Assembly, pays the Belgian membership fee, and gives financial support to the ACTRIS activities (including National Facility and Central Facility implementation and operations) by the federal partners in ACTRIS, which are KMI-IRM and BIRA-IASB. The other members of the ACTRIS-Belgium consortium have to seek financial support from their regional ministries, funding authorities, and host institutions. For now, they are supported only by their host institutions, as the regional ministries and funding authorities have not fully committed to supporting ACTRIS.

Users of ACTRIS

Key users include international organisations such as the European Space Agency (ESA), EUMETSAT, and Copernicus, which rely on the data for validation of their products and various atmospheric and environmental analyses. Federal and regional air quality government agencies in Belgium also utilise ACTRIS data. Additionally, researchers and academics within Belgian universities use ACTRIS data for their studies and projects.

ACTRIS-Bulgaria

National Contact Person:

Kalin Mutavchiev

Ministry of Education and Science of Bulgaria

Membership status in the ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly:

Member

Nominated delegates:

- Kalin Mutavchiev
- Tanja Dreischuh

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS:

- Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Bulgaria
- Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
- Bulgarian National Science Fund
- Research Performing Organisations involved in ACTRIS-BG

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium:

- Institute for Nuclear Research and Nuclear Energy, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (INRNE-BAS)
- Institute of Electronics, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (IE-BAS)

Highlights

INRNE-BAS is the coordinator of the National ACTRIS Consortium. BEO Moussala (INRNE-BAS) is an Aerosol In Situ National Facility and its team contributed also to the [JRC-EURDEP](#) (Radiological Data Exchange Platform); [eBAS](#) (atmospheric measurement data); [NRA](#) (Bulgarian Nuclear Regulatory Agency); [NOAA - GML](#) (The Global Monitoring Laboratory of the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration); - [WDCGG](#) WMO (The World Data Centre for Greenhouse Gases) by the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) under the Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW) programme of the World Meteorological Organization ([WMO](#)) international databases. The BEO Moussala Observatory Platform (INRNE-BAS) National Facility is in the process of labelling. The labelling procedure is planned for 2025.

The Sofia (IE-BAS) Aerosol Remote Sensing National Facility, hosted by the IE-BAS, started the labelling process in December 2023 and was successfully initially accepted in June 2024. Continuous sun-photometer and ceilometer measurements, as well as regular lidar measurements, are performed. Sun-photometer data are submitted to the AERONET database according to near-real-time protocols and are freely available online. After the raw data from the lidar measurements are processed by the Single Calculus Chain (SCC) algorithm, the resulting optical product data are sent to the publicly available EARLINET database. Sofia (IE-BAS) National Facility joined the E-PROFILE network in January 2024 and thus became the first Bulgarian site in this network. A fine dust measurement device for continuous and simultaneous monitoring of ambient PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ is also in operation. Installation of an integrating nephelometer for continuously monitoring the aerosol light scattering coefficient is planned for 2025.

ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
Basic Environmental Observatory Moussala - BEO Moussala (INRNE-BAS)	Observational Platform	42.179°N 23.585°E 2925 m a.s.l.	X					
Sofia - Institute of Electronics, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (IE-BAS)	Observational Platform	42.65°N 23.38°E 590 m a.s.l.				X		

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

The national consortium ACTRIS-BG was formally established in 2017 and acknowledged officially in June 2017 by the Bulgarian Ministry of Education and Science. It consists of two research organizations, the Institute for Nuclear Research and Nuclear Energy and the Institute of Electronics at the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, which are actively involved in ACTRIS-related research activities with their atmospheric measurement sites, which are also ACTRIS National Facilities. In Bulgaria, there is strong national support for ACTRIS activities. ACTRIS-BG has been on the National roadmap for research infrastructure since 2017, which is a clear sign of the national recognition of the conducted research.

 <https://actris-bg.eu/en/actris-bulgaria/>

Funding for ACTRIS

ACTRIS BG is included in the National Roadmap for Research Infrastructure 2020 – 2027 (NRRI). The Ministry of Education and Science (MoES) is the financial coordinator of NRRI and signs contracts with the coordinator and the partner organization (in the case of ACTRIS BG) for funding needed and allocated to the respective organization for the maintenance, upgrade and upscaling of the research infrastructure and relevant equipment (incl. hardware, software, licenses, operational costs, etc.).

Normally, these contracts are signed each year and have a duration of 24 months (1 + 1 year option). Duration can be extended, if the need for extension is justified and motivated adequately. This means that there could be two or more (if there are extensions) active projects and dedicated funding contracts with the coordinator or with the partner (ACTRIS BG). Each contract features a work plan and a financial plan submitted by the respective organization to MoES. This is meant to avoid duplication or improper overlapping of funds in the case of multiple active contracts.

Users of ACTRIS

The ACTRIS-BG measurement data are publicly available and are used by scientists, policymakers and the general public nationally and internationally. The main user community in Bulgaria is composed of researchers at various academic and educational institutions (including partners of ACTRIS-BG), as well as meteorological agencies, working on atmospheric research, weather forecasting and climate modelling, ecological research and air quality monitoring:

- Institute of Electronics
- Institute for Nuclear Research and Nuclear Energy
- National Institute of Geophysics, Geodesy and Geography
- Climate, Atmosphere and Water Research Institute
- National Institute for Meteorology and Hydrology
- St. Kliment Ohridski Sofia University
- Paisii Hilendarski University of Plovdiv

The Civil Aviation Administration and Air Traffic Services Authority are users of the volcanic ash observations by the Sofia (IE-BAS) high- and low-power lidars. Several stakeholders and policymakers dealing with the air quality in Bulgaria are also users of ACTRIS-BG data, e.g. Ministry of Environment and Water of Bulgaria, the Bulgarian Executive Environment Agency (ExEA), and Sofia Municipality.

ACTRIS-BG observational sites contribute to European and global networks such as WMO-GAW, AERONET, EARLINET, and E-PROFILE, providing data that are used for model development and verification.

МИНИСТЕРСТВО
НА ОБРАЗОВАНИЕТО
И НАУКАТА

ACTRIS-Cyprus

National Contact Person:

Jean Sciare

Climate & Atmosphere Research Centre director,
The Cyprus Institute

Membership status in the ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly:

Member

Nominated delegates:

- Michalis Mouskos
- Chrysanthos Savvides

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS:

- Deputy Ministry Research, Innovation and Digital Policy (DMRID)

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium:

- The Cyprus Institute (Cyl)
- ERASTOTHENES Centre of Excellence (EcoE)

MEMBER

Highlights

The Unmanned Systems Research Laboratory (USRL) is the largest drone facility in Cyprus and the Exploratory (Mobile) Platform of ACTRIS-Cyprus, providing novel drone-based solutions to extend the 4-dimensional exploration of the atmosphere.

In its endeavour to further develop as a “Technical Research Infrastructure”, USRL is continuously developing new products (drones) and services (UAV pilot training) to better support the Government of Cyprus in its missions to monitor the environment and comply with national policies and EU directives (e.g. early warning forest fire monitoring). These activities are strongly contributing to the long-term sustainability of the facility with stable (annual) sources of income. They also contribute to the development of new high-performance drones and technologies that further benefit the scientific community.

The Cyprus Atmospheric Observatory (CAO) is an Observatory Platform of ACTRIS-Cyprus. It is also developing as a regional flagship facility, herewith supporting several governments across the Eastern Mediterranean and Middle East (Cyprus, Egypt, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates) to develop national capacities on air pollution monitoring, through the provision of expert advice (consulting), technical training, and specialized environmental analyses. Beyond enhancing the financial sustainability of this Facility, the CAO is actively contributing to building a comprehensive regional atmospheric monitoring network and connecting it with ACTRIS.

Strongly supporting the post-graduate environmental programmes of the Cyprus Institute, CAO has also the ambition to become a regional hub of knowledge in atmospheric sciences; helping Middle Eastern countries to better monitor their atmospheric environment and better tackle societal challenges related to air pollution and climate change.

ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
Cyprus Atmospheric Observatory (CAO)	Observational Platform	35.039°N 33.058°E 550 m a.s.l.	X					
Cyprus Atmospheric Remote Sensing Observatory CARO	Observational Platform	34.675°N 33.043°E 50 m a.s.l.				X	X	
Unmanned Systems Research Laboratory (USRL)	Mobile Platform	Mobile	X					

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

ACTRIS-Cyprus has been enabled by two large European projects ([EMME-CARE](#) and [EXCELSIOR](#)), financially supported by the European Commission and the Cyprus Government. These two projects have led to the establishment of the CARE-C and ERASTOTHENES Centres of Excellence (CoEs), which are the two Research Performing Organisations operating ACTRIS observations in Cyprus. From mid-2026, these two CoEs will enter into a new stage of their life cycle putting sustainability at the heart of their next development phase. This will imply the further development of new services and products, herewith leveraging the recently established ACTRIS-Cyprus National Facilities (CAO, CARO, USRL) and promoting their exploitation to meet the needs of the scientific community, policymakers and industry.

Information on ACTRIS National Facilities can be found at respective National Facilities' websites: [CAO](#), [CARO](#), and [USRL](#).

Funding for ACTRIS

The Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digital Policy of the Republic of Cyprus is committed to financially contributing to the general support and operation support of ACTRIS-Cyprus. The Cyprus Institute is committed to financially contributing to the National Facility-based operation support for CAO and USRL. The Cyprus University and the ERASTOTHENES Center of Excellence are committed to financially contributing to the "National Facility-based operation support" for CARO.

All costs incurred by the daily operation of ACTRIS-Cyprus National Facilities include technical and scientific staff salaries, instrument operation/calibration/repair/maintenance/depreciation, and environmental expenses. These expenses are integrally supported by the two Research Performing Organisations operating the Cyprus facilities through extensive leveraging of soft funds such as competitive projects.

Users of ACTRIS

The main user community in Cyprus is composed of researchers at various academic and educational institutions (including partners of ACTRIS-Cyprus) working on atmospheric research, weather forecasting and climate modelling, ecological research, and air quality monitoring:

- Department of Labour Inspection (CAO National Facility - Aerosol chemical analyses)
- Department of Meteorology (CAO National Facility – co-location of meteorological observations from the national automatic weather station network)
- Department of Forests (USRL National Facility - drone surveillance of forest fires)

DEPUTY MINISTRY OF
RESEARCH, INNOVATION
AND DIGITAL POLICY
REPUBLIC OF CYPRUS

ACTRIS-Czech Republic

National Contact Person:

Jakub Ondráček

Research Group of Aerosol Chemistry and Physics, Institute of Chemical Process Fundamentals, Czech Academy of Sciences

Membership status in the ACTRIS ERIC

General Assembly:

Member

Nominated delegates:

- Vladimír Ždímal
- Jiří Švehla

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS:

- Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic
- Ministry of the Environment of the Czech Republic

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium:

- Czech Hydrometeorological Institute
- Institute of Chemical Process Fundamentals, Czech Academy of Sciences
- Global Change Research Institute, Czech Academy of Sciences (Czechglobe)
- RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University
- Institute of Atmospheric Physics, Czech Academy of Sciences

MEMBER

Highlights

ACTRIS Czech Republic actively contributes to atmospheric research and scientific collaboration through a range of initiatives. It organizes the ACTRIS Aerosol In Situ School and Open Door Day at **NAOK**, fostering education and public engagement. It supports the annual conference of the Czech Aerosol Society and conducts technical audits of national aerosol in situ facilities to ensure high-quality standards. In 2024 alone, 11 scientific results, including preprints, have been generated. ACTRIS Czech Republic is a key participant in major projects such as ATMO-ACCESS (2021–2025) and IRISCC (2024–2028) and maintains strong collaborations with national and European infrastructures, including EIRENE, RI-URBANS (2021–2025), MI-TRAP, and CAMS21a.

Contribution to the ACTRIS Central Facilities

Central Facility (CF)	CF Unit name	CF Unit description	CF Unit hosting institution
Centre for Aerosol In Situ measurements - European Center for Aerosol Calibration (CAIS-ECAC)	Prague Aerosol Calibration Centre	Calibration of Condensation Particle Counters Calibration of Mobility Particle Size Spectrometers Estimation of size resolved penetration of parts of sampling lines	Institute of Chemical Process Fundamentals, Czech Academy of Sciences

ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
Lom	Observational Platform	50.586°N 14.358°E 265 m a.s.l.	X					
Milešovka	Observational Platform	50.555°N 13.931°E 837 m a.s.l.		X				
National Atmospheric Observatory Kosetice	Observational Platform	49.573°N 15.08°E 536 m a.s.l.	X		X	X		
Suchdol	Observational Platform	50.127°N 14.385°E 277 m a.s.l.	X					

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

ACTRIS-CZ has been on a Roadmap of Large Research Infrastructures of the Czech Republic since 2016.

The latest version of the Czech Roadmap is available here: https://www.vyzkumne-infrastruktury.cz/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/Cestovni-mapa-VVI-2023-2026_elektronicka-verze.pdf

 <https://actris.cz/>

Social media: [Facebook](#) (Actris.cz)

Funding for ACTRIS

The latest update of the Roadmap of Large Research Infrastructures of the Czech Republic for the years 2023-2026 was acknowledged by the Czech Government on June 14th 2023. The Roadmap update was prepared following the resolution of the Government of the Czech Republic on public funding of large research infrastructures by 2026. Until 2015, besides the large research infrastructures approved for public funding by the Czech Government, the Roadmap included the prospective large research infrastructure projects. Since 2015, the Roadmap has included only the large research infrastructures adopted for public funding by the Government of the Czech Republic. As regards the financial support of such large research infrastructures, their operations costs are funded directly by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports (MEYS). The investment needs of large research infrastructures are then financed by the MEYS using European Structural and Investment Funds, currently from the Operational Programme Jan Amos Komenský (OP JAK). In this way, the Czech Republic applies a synergetic model of funding the operations and investment costs of large research infrastructures, using the state budget expenditures of the Czech Republic on research, development and innovation and the EU cohesion policy instruments.

Users of ACTRIS

The main user community in the Czech Republic is composed of researchers at various academic and educational institutions (including partners of ACTRIS-CZ), as well as stakeholders from municipalities and the industrial sector. In 2024, ACTRIS welcomed a diverse group of 174 users, including 91 researchers and developers, 76 university students, 5 stakeholder and municipal representatives, and 2 representatives from technological companies.

MUNI | RECETOX

MINISTRY OF EDUCATION,
YOUTH AND SPORTS

ÚSTAV CHEMICKÝCH
PROCESŮ AV ČR
INSTITUTE OF CHEMICAL
PROCESS FUNDAMENTALS
OF THE ASCR

INSTITUTE OF ATMOSPHERIC PHYSICS
CAS

ACTRIS-Denmark

National Contact Person:

Henrik Skov

Aarhus University, Department of Environmental Science, Roskilde

Membership status in the ACTRIS ERIC

General Assembly:

Member

Nominated delegate:

- Mads Rugaard Christensen

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS:

- Ministry of Higher Education and Research

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium:

- Aarhus University
- Danish Technological University
- University of Copenhagen

MEMBER

Highlights

ACTRIS-Denmark comprises two Observatory Platforms and two Exploratory Platforms, all of which are integrated into the ATMO-ACCESS project (2021-2025). Significant progress has been made with the construction of a new ACTRIS station at the Risoe site, alongside efforts to upgrade existing Observatory Platforms and implement procedures to meet ACTRIS labelling standards. The Copenhagen Exploratory Platform has been recommissioned, further enhancing the national infrastructure. Additionally, Denmark's active engagement in ACTRIS is reflected in the membership of Professor Bilde in the Atmospheric Simulation Chamber Committee (ACCC), contributing to the broader development of ACTRIS facilities.

ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
Aarhus University Research on Aerosols smog chamber facility (AURA)	Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	56.2°N 10.2°E 70 m a.s.l.	X					
University of Copenhagen; Photochemical reactor	Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	55.7°N 12.6°E 40 m a.s.l.	X	X	X			

Risoe Research Station	Observational Platform	55.63°N 12.1°E 5 m a.s.l.	X					
Villum Research Station	Observational Platform	81.6°N 16.7°W 24 m a.s.l.	X					

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

Before the end of the year, the scheme for labelling the two Danish Observatory Platforms will be submitted.

At the University of Copenhagen, a new Tenure Track Assistant Professor, Dr. Olga Garmash, has been hired to work on ACTRIS projects. She is currently focused on upgrading and recommissioning the experimental platform. A pre-study of the Observational Platform at the university revealed several challenges, including delays in the opening of the new building and the relocation of the Department of Chemistry, which is now expected to occur within the next 1–2 years. A site inspection further identified issues with the facility's physical layout, such as the proximity of ventilation from chemical fume hoods to the planned station. In light of these challenges, the decision was made to continue utilizing the existing monitoring station.

Funding for ACTRIS

Funding is ensured until the end of 2025 and an extension was asked from the ministry for a prolongation to ensure funding until the end of 2026. The reply is pending.

Users of ACTRIS

- ACTRIS-Denmark collaborates with a diverse range of users, including national public organizations such as NPO, industry partners like Force Technologies and the Danish Technological Institute, and research institutions such as NFA.
- It also supports innovation by engaging with start-ups like Devlabs, which specializes in environmental sensors, and Rensair, focusing on air cleaning technologies.
- In 2024, ACTRIS-Denmark provided a Transnational Access (TNA) opportunity at the AURA Exploratory Platform through the ATMO-ACCESS program (2021–2025).
- Additionally, recent developments at the AURA atmospheric simulation chamber—focused on characterizing chamber volume, air mixing, and charging—have been accepted for publication in Aerosol Science & Technology.

ACTRIS-Finland

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National Contact Person:

Katrianne Lehtipalo (ACTRIS-FI Director)

University of Helsinki, Finnish Meteorological Institute

National ACTRIS Coordinator:

Silja Häme

University of Helsinki

Membership status in the ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly:

Member

Member nominated delegates:

- Petteri Kauppinen
- Hannele Korhonen

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS:

- Research Council of Finland
- Ministry of Education and Culture
- Ministry of Transport and Communications

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium:

- University of Helsinki (UHEL)
- Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI)
- University of Eastern Finland (UEF)
- Tampere University (TAU)

MEMBER

Highlights

ACTRIS-FI flagship sites SMEAR II (Hyytiälä) and Pallas participated as pilot sites in ACTRIS National Facility labelling. These sites also contribute to other environmental ESFRIs (ICOS, eLTER, AnaEE), setting an example at the European level for co-located measurement stations. INAR RI (Integrated Atmospheric and Earth System Research Infrastructure) is the coordinating entity for the national activities of ACTRIS, ICOS, eLTER and AnaEE. INAR RI was selected in January 2025 as a 'lighthouse' research infrastructure to the updated national RI roadmap 2025-2028. Lighthouse status highlights that INAR RI is leading the way in all key infrastructure areas, such as service provision, impact, functionality and shared use.

ACTRIS-FI has a key role in responding to the new European Commission air quality directive. One of ACTRIS-FI National Facilities will be developed as a new air quality supersite (SMEAR III, Helsinki).

In addition to its ACTRIS National Facilities and contribution to the European level ACTRIS Central Facilities, ACTRIS-FI is actively involved in the RI developments at the European and international levels e.g., via several RI-related European Commission projects (ATMO-ACCESS (2021-2025), RI-URBANS (2021-2025), ENVRINNOV (2024-2026), CARGO-ACT (2024-2027), IRISCC (2024-2028) and providing access via the European Commission Trans National Access Program.

ACTRIS-FI facilities are the core data provider and a testbed for new technologies for companies in the field of aerosol, clouds and trace gases. The collaboration includes instrument prototyping and testing, instrument intercomparisons, benchmarking of new instrumentation and data provision for software developers. ACTRIS-FI activities have enabled the establishment of several spin-off companies (Airmodus Ltd, Karsa Ltd, MegaSense Ltd).

Contribution to the ACTRIS Central Facilities

Central Facility (CF)	CF Unit name	CF Unit description	CF Unit hosting institution
Data Centre (DC)	Cloud remote sensing data centre unit (CLU) and Data Discovery, Virtual Access and Services (DVAS)	Unit for data curation and other services for cloud remote sensing data.	Finnish Meteorological Institute
Centre for Cloud Remote Sensing (CCRES)	CCRES-FI	Unit for data processing and quality control for Doppler Wind Lidars, and training for users.	Finnish Meteorological Institute
Centre for Reactive Trace Gases In Situ Measurements (CiGas)	CiGas-UHEL	Unit for condensable vapor and aerosol precursor measurements using chemical ionization mass spectrometry (measurement and data quality assurance and control, training and consultancy and technology development)	University of Helsinki
Centre for Aerosol In Situ measurements-European Center for Aerosol Calibration (CAIS-ECAC)	Cluster Calibration Center (CCC)	Unit for nanoparticle number concentration and size distribution measurements (measurement and data quality assurance and control, training and consultancy and technology development)	University of Helsinki

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ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
Aerosol, cluster and trace gas laboratory	Laboratory Platform	60.2°N 24.967°E -	X		X			
FComLab - Doppler Cloud Radar	Mobile Platform	Mobile					X	
Kuopio Atmospheric Simulation Chambers (KASCs)	Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	62.9°N 27.633°E -	X					
Marambio	Observational Platform	64.25°S 56.63°W 198 m a.s.l.	X					
Aerosol and Trace Gas Mobile Laboratory (ATMo-Lab)	Mobile Platform	Mobile	X		X			
Multiwavelength Raman Lidar	Mobile Platform	Mobile				x		
Pallas Atmosphere-Ecosystem Supersite	Observational Platform	67.973°N 24.116°E 565 m a.s.l.	X	X	X		X	

SMEAR* II – Hyttiälä	Observational Platform	61.85°N 24.283°E 181 m a.s.l.	X		X	X	X	
FComLab - Doppler Lidar (FMI)	Mobile Platform	Mobile					X	
SMEAR I – Värriö	Observational Platform	67.767°N 29.583°E 400 m a.s.l.	X	X	X			
SMEAR IV – Kuopio	Observational Platform	62.9°N 27.65°E 306 m a.s.l.	X	X				
Unmanned Aerial vehicle (UAV)	Mobile Platform	Mobile	X	X				
Utö Atmospheric and Marine Research Station	Observational Platform	59.7806°N 21.373°E 8 m a.s.l.	X					

**Station for Measuring Ecosystem-Atmospheric Relations (SMEAR), continuous measurements of the relationship of atmosphere and forest in a boreal climate zone. The SMEAR stations I-IV are unique entities in the world with their comprehensive measurements at their respective locations (www.atm.helsinki.fi/SMEAR).*

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

ACTRIS-FI has 14 ACTRIS National Facilities and contributes to ACTRIS European-level operations by hosting several Central Facility units. There is a strong national support for ACTRIS in Finland. ACTRIS-FI, as part of INAR RI (Integrated Atmospheric and Earth System Research Infrastructure), has been on the Finnish RI Roadmap since 2014, and INAR RI received a national RI ‘lighthouse’ status in 2025 (see more in the highlights).

 <https://www.helsinki.fi/en/infrastructures/actris-finland>

Social Media: [LinkedIn](#) (ACTRIS), [BlueSky](#) (@actris.bsky.social),

Funding for ACTRIS

ACTRIS-Finland operations are mainly funded by the host organizations: the University of Helsinki, the Finnish Meteorological Institute, the University of Eastern Finland and Tampere University. Finnish ministries (Ministry of Education and Culture via the Research Council of Finland and Ministry of Transport and Communications) and the European Commission are also notably supporting ACTRIS-FI activities. There are currently four ongoing RI projects funded by the Research Council of Finland supporting the upgrading of ACTRIS-FI stations and platforms and the operations and development of the University of Helsinki Central Facility Units. ACTRIS-FI is also supported by the Research Council of Finland research and impact flagship ACCC (Atmosphere and Climate Competence Center) which involves all ACTRIS-FI partner organizations. There are several EU RI projects to which ACTRIS-FI organizations are contributing: ATMO-ACCESS (2021-2025), RI-URBANS (2021-2025), CARGO-ACT (2024-2027), ENVRINNOV (2024-2026) and IRISCC (2024-2028).

Users of ACTRIS

- The user base of ACTRIS-FI includes scientists, students, air quality experts, instrument manufacturers and software developers. They actively use ACTRIS-FI measurement stations and platforms (physical access and data access). There are approximately 1500 ACTRIS-related access (research visitor) days, incl. national and international users, at the National Facilities annually.
- ACTRIS-FI capacity is actively used by the ACTRIS-FI consortium, with around 400 students and scientists in the field of aerosol, clouds and reactive trace gases.
- The university partners of ACTRIS-FI provide multidisciplinary master's and doctoral programmes in the field of atmospheric sciences with around 10 MSc and 10 PhD degrees completed each year.
- There are several ACTRIS-related training courses for master and doctoral students organized at the SMEAR II station (Hyytiälä, Finland) annually – bringing at least around 100 students from Finland and all around the world each year to Hyytiälä to learn from ACTRIS-related measurements.
- Currently, ACTRIS-FI actively collaborates with 20 companies. The collaboration includes instrument prototyping and testing, instrument calibrations (joint organization of calibration workshops), benchmarking of new instrumentation and data provision for software developers. There is also a new collaboration with several companies related to indoor air filtering and air quality, air pollutant emissions and drone measurements.

ACTRIS-France

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National Contact Person:

Stephane Sauvage (ACTRIS-FR Director)

IGE - Université Grenoble-Alpes

Membership status in the ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly

Member

Nominated delegates:

- Jean Marie Flaud, Chair of the GA
- Jérôme Rose

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS

- Ministère de l'Enseignement Supérieur de la Recherche (MESR)
- Centre National de Recherche Scientifique (CNRS)
- Centre National d'Etudes Spatiales (CNES)
- Commissariat à l'Energie Atomique et aux Energies Alternatives (CEA)
- Institut de Recherche pour le Développement (IRD)
- Institut Mines-Télécom Nord Europe (IMT NE)
- Institut National de l'Environnement Industriel et des Risques (INERIS)
- Météo France (MF)
- Aix-Marseille Université (AMU)
- École des Ponts ParisTech (ENPC)
- Ecole Polytechnique (EP)
- Université Clermont Auvergne (UCA)
- Université Grenoble-Alpes (UGA)
- Université de Lille (ULILLE)
- Université d'Orléans (UO)
- Université Paris-Est Créteil (UPEC)
- Université Paris Cité (UPCité)
- Université de Toulouse (UT)
- Université de la Réunion (UR)
- Université Versailles St. Quentin (UVSQ)

Research performing organizations in the national ACTRIS consortium

- Centre National de Recherche Scientifique (CNRS)
- Centre National d'Etudes Spatiales (CNES)
- Commissariat à l'Energie Atomique et aux Energies Alternatives (CEA)
- Institut de Recherche pour le Développement (IRD)
- Institut Mines-Télécom Nord Europe (IMT NE)
- Institut National de l'Environnement Industriel et des Risques (INERIS)
- Institut Paul-Emile-Victor (IPEV)
- Institut Polytechnique de Grenoble (Grenoble-INP)
- Météo France (MF)
- Aix-Marseille Université (AMU)
- École des Ponts ParisTech (ENPC)
- Ecole Normale Supérieure (ENS)
- Ecole Polytechnique (EP)
- Sorbonne Université (SU)
- Université Clermont Auvergne (UCA)
- Université Grenoble-Alpes (UGA)
- Université de Lille (ULILLE)
- Université d'Orléans (UO)
- Université Paris-Est Créteil (UPEC)
- Université Paris Cité (UPCité)
- University of Toulouse (UT)
- Université de la Réunion (UR)
- Université Versailles St. Quentin (UVSQ)

Highlights

France hosted the ACTRIS Scientific Conference in Rennes on 13-16 May 2024. The ACTRIS-France office significantly contributed to the organisation and the success of this event which brought together more than 350 international scientists in the atmospheric field.

Over the past years, ACTRIS-FR has grown into a more consolidated community, working closely on various national projects involving several RIs (such as Obs4Clim together with ICOS-FR and IAGOS) and actively participating in European projects for the development of the RI such as ATMO-ACCESS (2021-2025), CAMS2_21a, KADI, RI-URBANS (2021-2025), ENVRINNOV (2024-2026), CARGO-ACT (2024-2027), IRISCC (2024-2028). Notably, in the frame of RI-Urbans, service tools have been developed for Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC), source apportionment, and Oxidative Potential (OP).

ACTRIS-FR organised its annual workshop in Oléron (France) in October 2024 gathering around 80 participants (researchers, engineers) onsite and online.

The Laboratoire de Météorologie Physique / Observatoire Physique de Clermont-Ferrand (UCA & CNRS) has been approved as the new host for the Topical Centre unit for Cloud in Situ Measurements (CIS) "Centre for Cloud Particle properties (CCPar)", to support and ensure the measurements and data provision of essential cloud in situ variables within ACTRIS.

The French Central Facility units ACMCC and CiGas have dedicated substantial efforts to provide user-friendly tools to the community for the submission of near real-time data (NRT). This has enhanced the representation of NRT data in the ACTRIS Data Centre (DC) and supported the development of innovative services, such as added-value products like source apportionment.

The ACTRIS-FR Data Centre AERIS has actively participated in the release of the new version of the ACTRIS data portal. It is responsible for managing remote sensing data for reactive gases, measurements from atmospheric simulation chambers and a significant part of remote sensing and in situ aerosol data.

Contribution to the ACTRIS Central Facilities

Central Facility (CF)	CF Unit name	CF Unit description	CF Unit hosting institution
Centre for Aerosol In Situ - European Center for Aerosol Calibration (CAIS-ECAC)	Aerosol Chemical Monitor Calibration Center (ACMCC)	ECAC Deputy lead Building capacity for high-quality in situ chemical characterization of aerosols, as part of CAIS-ECAC central facility. Carrying out activities related to the development of guidelines and service tools, training and consultancy, as well as innovation. Organizing intercomparison campaigns and technical workshops. Data reporting. Offering capacity building opportunities through the exchange of information between manufacturers and users, the optimization of technological solutions, and the evaluation of new online aerosol chemical analyzers.	The French National Institute for Industrial Environment and Risks (INERIS), French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS), French Alternative Energies and Atomic Energy Commission (CEA)
Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing (CARS)	Automatic Sun/ sky/ lunar Photometers (ASP-FR)	CARS Deputy lead Provision of services related to characterization, calibration, maintenance of automatic sun/ sky/lunar photometers and training of users	French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS), Université de Lille (ULILLE)

Centre for Cloud In Situ (CIS)	Center for Cloud Particle Properties (CCPar)	Development of instrument specific calibration procedures for droplet spectrometer, development of data quality control and measurement guidelines, audit / labelling support for CIS NFs	French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS), Université Clermont Auvergne (UCA)
Centre for Cloud Remote Sensing (CCRES)	CCRES-FR	CCRES lead Management and coordination of the consortium, development of DCR, disdrometer and ALC calibration procedures, development of quality control package for DCRs and ALCs, Labelling process of NFs, Development of data quality control in support of labelling, Training of NF staff and users, organisation of workshops, Testing of new instruments, CCRES communication	French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS), École Polytechnique (EP), Université de Versailles Saint-Quentin-en-Yvelines (UVSQ)
Centre for Reactive trace Gases In Situ Measurements (CiGas)	CiGas-IMT	CiGas deputy lead: Leading, managing and coordinating activities of OVOCs, and contributing to NMHC and NOx: provision of measurement guidelines, training, audit and labelling. Participation to CEN WG13 on ozone precursors, and other communities. Method development and test of new instruments/variables. Organization of side by side intercomparison for OVOCs	Institut Mines-Télécom Nord Europe (IMT NE)
Centre for Reactive Trace Gases Remote Sensing (CREGARS)	UVVIS-FR	Management and coordination of activities concerning UVVIS SAOZ-type for ozone and NO2 columns. Provision of measurements by a centralised retrieval, guidelines, procedures, individual training, audit and labelling. Interaction with the NDACC community.	French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS), Université de Versailles Saint-Quentin-en-Yvelines (UVSQ)
Centre for Reactive Trace Gases Remote Sensing (CREGARS)	O3DIAL-FR	Management and coordination of activities concerning LIDAR for ozone profiling. Provision of guidelines, procedures, training, audit and labelling. Interaction with the NDACC community	French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS)
Data Centre (DC)	Data Discovery, Virtual Access and Services (DVAS)	ACTRIS DC Deputy lead DVAS is responsible for organising access to measurement data from the topic data centre units, and documentation of procedures as support to observational and exploratory National Fs. The DVAS unit provides the ACTRIS web interface for	French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS), Université de Lille (ULILLE), Université Paris-Est Créteil (UPEC), Université de Toulouse (UT)

		data download, services and digital tools as well as performing data production of Level 3 data, and synergy data products.	
Data Centre (DC)	Aerosol Remote Sensing DC unit (ARES)	The ARES data centre unit provides data curation and data processing service for aerosol remote sensing data coming from lidar and photometer observations. This includes centralised processing, traceability, harmonisation and data versioning, quality control, data archiving in EARLINET DB, data provision and documentation. The unit allows for NRT data provisioning and offers support and training activities. Furthermore, level 3 data production for climatological analysis and the delivery of new data products are offered.	French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS), Université de Lille (ULILLE)
Data Centre (DC)	Atmospheric simulation chamber DC unit (ASC)	The ASC data centre unit provides data curation service for data obtained from experiments in atmospheric simulation chambers (ACTRIS Exploratory Platforms). This includes tools for harmonised data and metadata submission. The ASC unit is structured in three pillars : the Database of Atmospheric Simulation Chamber Studies (DASCS) providing access to experimental data (level 2 data), The Library of Analytical Resources (LAR) for quantitative analytical resources (level 3 data) and the Library of Advanced Data Products (LADP) for mature data products (level 3 data).	French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS), Université Paris-Est Créteil (UPEC)
Data Centre (DC)	Trace Gases Remote Sensing DC unit (GRES)	The GRES data centre unit provides data curation service for reactive trace gases remote sensing data. This includes standardised processes for metadata and data submission, traceability, data versioning, quality control, inclusion of data in the database, data provision and archiving, and documentation. In addition, it offers production of level 3 data for climatological analysis and added value products (quicklooks, links to EVDC-ESA Atmospheric Validation Data Centre). All data is stored in the GRES database which is hosted by the French data centre for atmospheric data AERIS.	French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS)

ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
Atmospheric Observatory of LiLle (ATOLL)	Observational Platform	50.612°N 3,142°E 60 m a.s.l.	X			X		
Chambre de simulation atmosphérique à irradiation naturelle d'Orléans (HELIOS)	Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	47.838°N 1.944°E -	X		X			
Multiphase Atmospheric Simulation Chamber (CESAM)	Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	48,789 2,444 -	X		X			
Observatoire de Haute Provence (OHP-GEO)	Observational Platform	43.924°N 5.718°E 650 m a.s.l.				X		
OPAR Observatoire de Physique de l'Atmosphère à La Réunion	Observational Platform	21,079°S 55,383°E 2160 m a.s.l.	X			X	X	X
Pyrenean Platform for Observation of the Atmosphere (P2OA)	Observational Platform	42.936°N 0.142°E 2877 m a.s.l.	X		X			
Site d'observation atmosphériques Puy de Dôme/ Opme/Cézeaux (COPDD)	Observational Platform	45.772°N 2.965°E 1465 m a.s.l.	X		X	X		
Site Instrumental de Recherche par Télédétection Atmosphérique (SIRTA)	Observational Platform	48.717°N 2.207°E 160 m a.s.l.	X		X	X	X	

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

ACTRIS-FR has been on the French National Roadmap since 2016. ACTRIS-FR operates under a consortium agreement signed by 23 organisations. The governance structure comprises 4 different bodies: a general assembly, a head office, an executive board and a scientific advisory group.

www.actris.fr

Social media: [Bluesky](#) (@actris.bsky.social)

Funding for ACTRIS

Global annual operation costs in 2023 are estimated at 17 M€ (including costs for investment, operations, and staff), representing 89 full-time equivalent employees. The costs are the results of an annual full cost calculation based on a national methodology provided by the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research.

ACTRIS-France is mainly funded by the participating 23 host organizations, CNRS being the most important contributor (>30%). The Ministry of Higher Education and Research furthermore supports the structured implementation of ACTRIS-FR. A major national project ANR/Equipex+/Obs4Clim (2021-2028) provides funding to upgrade the national platforms of ACTRIS-FR, ICOS-FR, and IAGOS-FR, intending to support the development of new technologies toward a future atmospheric observing system.

In addition, the ACTRIS-FR consortium significantly contributes to the development of the RI and provision of access to ACTRIS facilities and services through several EU RI projects: ATMO-ACCESS (2021-2025), RI-URBANS (2021-2025), KADI (2022-2025), CARGO-ACT (2024-2027), ENVRINNOV (2024-2026), IRISCC (2024-2028), as well as the Copernicus project CAMS2_21a.

Users of ACTRIS

- At least 30 research institutes specialising in atmospheric and climate research represent a community of several thousand researchers and engineers who are primary users of ACTRIS data and services. Each year, more than 100 peer-reviewed scientific articles and 10 PhD theses are produced by the ACTRIS-FR community and are related to French Observational/Exploratory Platforms or Central Facility units.
- Each year, several national initiatives (e.g., via calls from national research agencies, national research programmes, and space agencies) and European research projects engage the ACTRIS-FR community, providing access to platforms, services, and data.
- Private companies such as instrument manufacturers (for example Picarro, Tofwerk, Aerodyne, Droplet Measurement Technologies, TSI, etc) use the national facilities for developing, testing, and validating new instruments and methodologies for atmospheric observations.
- Through the RI-Urbans project (2021-2025), ACTRIS-FR takes part in developing new useful services for air quality agencies. The French ACTRIS community brings expertise to these operational networks, especially for the implementation of the newly revised EU Ambient Air Quality Directive.
- ACTRIS data and services support international monitoring networks such as AERONET, NDACC, EMEP, and GAW.

ACTRIS-Germany

National Contact Person:

Ulla Wandinger

Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research (TROPOS)

Membership status in the ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly:

Member

Nominated delegates:

- Jochen Elberskirch
- Jonas Esche

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS:

- Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF)
- Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection (BMUV)
- Federal Ministry for Digital and Transport (BMDV)
- German Environment Agency (UBA)

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium:

- Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research (TROPOS)
- Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research (AWI)
- Bergische Universität Wuppertal (BUW)
- Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD)
- Forschungszentrum Jülich GmbH (FZJ)
- Goethe-Universität Frankfurt am Main (GUF)
- Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)
- Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München (LMU)
- German Environment Agency (UBA)
- Universität Bremen (UBRE)
- University of Cologne (UoC)

Highlights

HOCEANET-Atmosphere at Neumayer III Station, Antarctica

In January 2024, the COALA campaign ended after collecting one year of data at the Neumayer III station in Antarctica. Continuous lidar and radar measurements were performed with the TROPOS mobile remote sensing facility OCEANET-Atmosphere to characterize aerosol properties and cloud structures in one of the cleanest environments on Earth. The first results have been published in the Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society.

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ACTRIS aerosol and cloud remote sensing at Cabo Verde

In the summer of 2024, the TROPOS remote sensing station at the Ocean Science Center in Mindelo, Cabo Verde was completed. It performs continuous observations of aerosols, clouds and radiation. In August and September, the station contributed to the international ORCESTRA campaign dedicated to Organized Convection and EarthCARE Studies over the Tropical Atlantic. It is also participating in the ATMO-ACCESS pilot study (2021-2025) to provide access to international stakeholders in support of the validation of EarthCARE.

Daytime increase of stratospheric NOx

At Zugspitze, reactive trace gases are remotely observed using solar FTIR spectrometry. Two recently published KIT papers show that this approach is the only way to measure stratospheric NOx from the ground. From the multi-year data set, scaling factors describing the daytime increase of stratospheric NOx were derived and the seasonal change of this increase was shown for the first time. The data are in excellent agreement with the latest photochemical model results and provide an important basis for improved satellite retrievals of tropospheric NOx.

Experiments at the atmospheric simulation chamber SAPHIR

In the summer of 2024, experiments were carried out in the SAPHIR chamber mimicking conditions in the Delhi urban area. Groups from the Universities of Birmingham and Nottingham joined forces with Airyx, a company specializing in novel gas sensing technologies. Conditions in the chamber were pushed to 'extreme' pollution events, comparable to those observed during field campaigns in Delhi. This allowed Airyx's instruments to be tested in a wide range of chemical regimes, ensuring their stability and durability for long-term measurements in a variety of environments.

Mobile platform LACROS in Eriswil, Switzerland

During winter 2023/2024, the TROPOS mobile platform LACROS demonstrated its mobile capabilities in the campaign of the ERC project CLOUDLAB, led by ETH Zürich. Funded by the DFG project PolarCAP, LACROS joined the CLOUDLAB team to investigate ice formation processes in the natural lab of persistent supercooled stratus clouds, which dominate the sky in the subalpine region of Switzerland at this time of the year.

Boundary-layer measurement campaign at JOYCE

In the summer of 2024, the JOYCE observatory operated by UoC in Jülich hosted the VITAL I measurement campaign and a summer school on boundary-layer profiling with around 50 participants as part of the Hans-Ertel-Zentrum for Weather Research (HERZ), in cooperation with the DWD and several German universities. The focus of the campaign was on the vertical structure of the troposphere in order to close the observational gap of wind, water vapour and temperature profiles in the atmospheric boundary layer.

First field campaign of the new mobile platform KLOCX

In September 2024, KLOCX (KIT) instrumentation was set up in the Inn Valley, Austria, to participate in the international TEAMx research programme, which aims at improving the understanding of exchange processes in the atmosphere over mountains. KLOCX measurements focus on new insights into the life-cycle phases of fog and low-level clouds.

Contribution to the ACTRIS Central Facilities

Central Facility (CF)	CF Unit name	CF Unit description	CF Unit hosting institution
Centre for Reactive Trace Gases Remote Sensing (CREGARS)	CREGARS-FTIR-DE	Provision of instrument specific training of operation and maintenance, support in QA/QC of the ACTRIS certified NFs, contribution to labelling of ACTRIS NFs, maintenance of the retrieval software SFIT4.	University of Bremen
Centre for Cloud In Situ Measurements (CIS)	Center for Cloud Ice Nucleation (CCIce)	Leading CIS activities, QA/QC support for ice nucleating particle (INP) instruments, including calibration and validation services and the provision of guidelines, trainings and workshops.	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
Centre for Cloud In Situ Measurements (CIS)	Centre for Cloud Water Chemistry (CCWaC)	Provision of calibration and standardization services as well as QA/QC for cloud water chemical analysis	Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research
Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing (CARS)	ALC-DWD	Contribution to QA/QC for ALC, contribution to labeling of ALC in CCRES, operation of ALC testbed	German Meteorological Service
Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing (CARS)	ALC-LMU	Contribution to QA/QC for ALC, contribution to labeling of CCRES NFs, operation of ALC testbed	Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München
Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing (CARS)	AHL-LMU	Contribution to QA/QC for AHL, contribution to the labelling of ARS NFs, organizing and participating in intercomparison campaigns and site audits	Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München
Centre for Aerosol In Situ Measurements-European Center for Aerosol Calibration (CAIS-ECAC)	Organic Tracers and Aerosol Constituents - Calibration Centre (OGTAC-CC)	Leading CAIS activities, provision of calibration and standardization services, QA/QC operation support and services and training on the analysis of particulate organic marker compounds	Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research
Centre for Aerosol In Situ Measurements-European Center for Aerosol Calibration (CAIS-ECAC)	World Calibration Centre for Aerosol Physics (WCCAP)	Provision of calibration and standardization services, QA/QC operation support and services and training on microphysical and optical instruments	Leibniz Institute for Tropospheric Research

Centre for Cloud Remote Sensing (CCRES)	CCRES-DE	Provision of microwave radiometer (MWR) data processing tools, QA/QC, retrieval algorithms, training for MWR operators	University of Cologne
Centre for Reactive Trace Gases In Situ Measurements (CiGas)	CiGas-FZJV	Leading CiGas activities, QA/QC for VOC measurements, provision of standard measurements, audits and round robins, performing NF labelling	Forschungs-zentrum Jülich
Centre for Reactive Trace Gases In Situ Measurements (CiGas)	CiGas-FZJN	QA/QC for NO _x measurements, provision of standard measurements, audits and instrument intercomparisons	Forschungs-zentrum Jülich
Centre for Reactive Trace Gases In Situ Measurements (CiGas)	CiGas-DWD	Contributions to calibration and standardization services, supporting intercomparisons and QA/QC for VOC and NO _x measurements.	German Meteorological Service

ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
Aerosol from Ground to Cloud Mobile Experiment (ACME)	Mobile Platform	Mobile	X	X				
Aerosol Interaction and Dynamics in the Atmosphere (AIDA and AIDA-dynamic)	Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	49.09°N 8.42°E 110 m a.s.l.	X	X				
Atmosphere Simulation Chamber (SAPHIR)	Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	50.9°N 6.41°E 90 m a.s.l.	X		X			
Atmospheric Chemistry Department - Chamber (ACD-C)	Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	51.35°N 12.43°E 120 m a.s.l.	X		X			
Bremen	Observational Platform	53.1°N 8.85°E 27 m a.s.l.						X
Cape Verde Atmospheric Observatory (CVAO)	Observational Platform	16.87°N 24.87°W 9 m a.s.l.	X		X	X	X	
Dushanbe, Tajikistan	Observational Platform	38.56°N 68.86°E 864 m a.s.l.				X		
Garmisch-Partenkirchen/Zugspitze/Schneefernerhaus	Observational Platform	47.48°N 11.06°E 743 m a.s.l.	X			X		X

Jülich Observatory for Cloud Evolution (JOYCE)	Observational Platform	50.908°N 6.413°E 111 m a.s.l.					X	
Karlsruhe Low-Cloud Exploratory Platform (KLOCX)	Mobile Platform	Mobile		X			X	
Leipzig Aerosol and Cloud Remote Observations System (LACROS)	Mobile Platform	Mobile				X	X	
Melpitz Research Station	Observational Platform	51.525°N 12.928°E 86 m a.s.l.	X		X	X	X	
Meteorological Observatory Hohenpeißenberg	Observational Platform	47.801°N 11.01°E 990 m a.s.l.	X		X	X		
Meteorological Observatory Lindenberg	Observational Platform	52.209°N 14.129°E 104 m a.s.l.					X	
Mobile FTIR spectrometer	Mobile Platform	Mobile						X
München	Observational Platform	48.148°N 11.573°E 539 m a.s.l.				X	X	
Ny-Ålesund, Spitsbergen	Observational Platform	78.92°N 11.92°E 23 m a.s.l.				X		X
OCEANET-Atmosphere	Mobile Platform	Mobile				X		
Paramaribo, Suriname	Observational Platform	5.81°N 55.21°W 7 m a.s.l.						X
Quartz Glass Reactor (QUAREC)	Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	51.24°N 7.15°E 240 m a.s.l.	X		X			
Schmücke	Observational Platform	50.65°N 10.77°E 937 m a.s.l.	X	X	X			
Taunus Observatory	Observational Platform	50.22°N 8.45°E 825 m a.s.l.	X		X			
Turbulent Leipzig Aerosol Cloud Interaction Simulator (LACIS-T)	Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	51.35°N 12.43°E 120 m a.s.l.	X	X				
Waldhof	Observational Platform	52.801°N 10.757°E 74 m a.s.l.	X		X			

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

ACTRIS-D has been included in the National Roadmap for Research Infrastructures in 2019.

 <https://www.fona.de/en/measures/research-infrastructures/actris-d.php>

 <https://www.tropos.de/en/research/actris-d>

Funding for ACTRIS

The implementation of ACTRIS-D is funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) under the FONA Strategy "Research for Sustainability". The operation of the Central Facilities is supported by the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Nuclear Safety and Consumer Protection (BMUV). Contributions of the German Meteorological Service (DWD) are funded by the Federal Ministry of Digital and Transport (BMDV). Both the implementation and operation of ACTRIS-D are co-funded by the German Research Performing Organisations.

Users of ACTRIS

In Germany, more than 20 universities and about 20 non-university research institutes of the Helmholtz Association, the Leibniz Association and the Max Planck Society are involved in atmospheric and climate research, satellite remote sensing and air pollution assessment, representing a community of several thousand researchers, engineers and students can benefit from ACTRIS data and services. The main organisational users are the German Meteorological Service (DWD), other research infrastructures such as ICOS ERIC and IAGOS-AISBL, the German Federal Environmental Agency (UBA) and various state environmental protection agencies.

Jahre
Umweltbundesamt
1974–2024

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HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FÜR POLAR-
UND MEERESFORSCHUNG

Leibniz Institute for
Tropospheric Research

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based on a decision of
the German Bundestag

ACTRIS-Italy

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National Contact Person:

Lucia Mona

National Research Council of Italy

Membership status in the ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly:

Member

Nominated delegates:

- Mauro Bertelletti
- Gelsomina Pappalardo, Vice-Chair

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS:

- Italian Ministry of Research and Education
- Italian Ministry of Environment and Energy Security.
- Regions in which territory ACTRIS national and/or central facilities are located (Abruzzo Region, Basilicata Region, Campania Region, Emilia Romagna Region, Lazio Region, Liguria Region, Puglia Region, Sicilia Region)

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium:

- CNR - National Research Council of Italy
- INFN – Italian National Institute for Nuclear Physics
- ENEA - Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development
- University “Federico II” of Naples
- University of L’Aquila
- University “Sapienza” of Rome
- University of Salento
- University of Urbino

MEMBER

Highlights

In the last 5-6 years, the ACTRIS-IT team has grown into a more consolidated community, working closely on various National projects involving the different ACTRIS-IT partners (such as Per-ACTRIS-IT and ITINERIS) and co-participating in European Projects like RI-URBANS (2021-2025).

The Italian ACTRIS community contributed to advancing knowledge in aerosol formation and typing. Long-time trend analysis of nucleation events at Southern Italy coastal sites have been investigated, and methodologies for aerosol typing and source apportionment have been developed and tested. Aerosol typing is one of the topics of interest to air quality management authorities as understanding how sources contribute to the presence of aerosols is important to identify actions to reduce their impacts. The link with Italian local authorities for environmental protection has been reinforced thanks to the ACTRIS-IT activities in regional, national and EU projects. An example is the campaign carried out in the Po Valley to

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showcase the relevance of ACTRIS measurements of Ultrafine and Black Carbon particles.

The ACTRIS-IT community highly contributes also to the desert dust particle investigation: the high expertise of the ACTRIS-IT team allowed the exploitation of a mineral dust reanalysis model for assessing its reliability, allowing the model exploitation in combination with satellite and ground-based measurements and extracting information about impact at the ground in terms of PM10. In addition, ACTRIS-IT members were coauthors (and principal author) of a review paper about the current observational capability of mineral dust particles, discussing dust observational gaps at a global level to address the needs of different users, from research communities to non-scientific stakeholders.

A new topic addressed by the ACTRIS-IT community is the link between suspended particles and bacteria/viruses: ACTRIS-IT has been pioneering in this field proposing a quantitative experimental protocol to study the correlation between air quality and survival of aero-dispersed bacteria.

Finally, during the COVID-19 pandemic, ACTRIS-IT investigated the impact of societal restrictions on surface O3 at several high-elevation sites across North America and Western Europe (among which Monte Cimone).

Contribution to the ACTRIS Central Facilities

Central Facility (CF)	CF Unit name	CF Unit description	CF Unit hosting institution
Head Office (HO)	Service Access Management Unit (SAMU)	SAMU is a unit of the ACTRIS Head Office dedicated to the management of the physical and remote access process to the entire European IR. Access is regulated by the ACTRIS access policy and is implemented through the ACTRIS Access management Plan.	National Research Council
Data Centre (DC)	Data Discovery, Virtual Access and Services (DVAS)	The ACTRIS Data Discovery, Virtual Access and Services unit (DVAS) is responsible for organising access to measurement data from the topic data centre units, and documentation of procedures as support to observational and exploratory NFs.	National Research Council
Data Centre (DC)	Aerosol remote sensing data centre unit (ARES)	<p>The ARES data centre unit provides data curation and data processing service for aerosol remote sensing data coming from lidar and photometer observations. The unit allows for RRT and NRT data provisioning and offers support and training activities.</p> <p>The main goal is to provide access to high-quality and documented datasets of the aerosol optical properties vertical distribution in the whole troposphere and upper stratosphere with short time resolution.</p>	National Research Council

Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing (CARS)	AHL-CNR	The unit uses AHL (aerosol high power lidar) to provide profile aerosol optical properties (aerosol backscatter coefficient, aerosol extinction coefficient and aerosol linear depolarization ratio) at one or more wavelengths, allowing subsequent calculation of several spectral parameters (Angstrom exponents, lidar ratios) of the lofted aerosol layers, and therefore aerosol typing. The unit offers an advanced laboratory for the characterization of instruments and components, and the calculation of calibration and correction factors. A fixed reference instrument is operated and used for direct comparison with the user's field instruments.	Institute of Methodologies for Environmental Analysis
Centre for Aerosol In Situ measurements (CAIS)	Elemental Mass Calibration Centre (EMC2)	The unit is in charge of chemical and element aerosol characterization. EMC2 is devoted to the analysis of the elemental composition of aerosols, environmental samples and cultural heritage by means of analytical nuclear techniques, such as ion beam analysis, besides other fields of applications, for instance, material science and forensics, and radiocarbon dating with accelerator mass spectrometry.	National Institute for Nuclear Physics

ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
Atmospheric Rome joint supersitE	Observational Platform	41.88°N 12.68°E 107 m a.s.l.				X		
ChAMBRé	Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	44.403°N 8.972°E 40 m a.s.l.	X		X			
CIAO	Observational Platform	40.6°N 15.72°E 760 m a.s.l.	X			X	X	X
CIAO Mobile Facility	Mobile Platform	Mobile				X	X	

Lampedusa	Observational Platform	35.518°N 12.63°E 45 m a.s.l.				X	X	
Lecce (ECO-CNR + UNISALENTO)	Observational Platform	40.336°N 18.124°E 36 m a.s.l.	X		X	X		
MAGA Mobile facility	Mobile Platform	Mobile	X		X			
Naples Fixed National Facility	Observational Platform	40.838°N 14.183°E 118 m a.s.l.	X			X		
UNIAQ/CETEMPS	Observational Platform	42.368°N 13.351°E 656 m a.s.l.				X	X	

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

Eight Italian institutions, both Universities and Research Performing Organizations, have been working on ACTRIS-related research activities for about 15 years within several research and collaboration projects. The national consortium has been organized as a Joint Research Unit named ACTRIS Italy (ACTRIS- IT), formally established in October 2017 and acknowledged officially in September 2018 by the Italian Ministry of Research and Education. The governance bodies of ACTRIS-IT are the General Assembly, already established, which is the major decision body, and a coordination team for day-to-day management. All the parties of the JRU contribute in terms of human and instrumental resources.

Italy has a National Roadmap for Research Infrastructures named "[Piano Nazionale Infrastruttura di Ricerca \(PNIR\) 2021 – 2027](#)" published on 20/10/2021 by the National Ministry of University and Research. The PNIR provides strategic orientation for policies related to the crucial topic of Research Infrastructures and aims to provide greater detail on a technical-strategic level, defining and updating national priorities. The PNIR identifies the priority research infrastructures for Italy by adopting, for this purpose, European methods and criteria, and provides the possibility of systematizing what is already present in Italy. ACTRIS is part of the National Roadmap as high priority research infrastructure.

 <https://actris.it/>

Social media: [X \(@ACTRIS_IT\)](#)

Funding for ACTRIS

In 2023 the implementation project of ACTRIS Italy, PER-ACTRIS-IT, was completed. The project was funded with 20M€ under a competitive call for proposals in the framework of the National Operational Programming Period 2014- 2020 ("Programma Operativo Nazionale Ricerca e Innovazione 2014-2020" (PON R&I)).

The operation of ACTRIS is supported through an annual national contribution (FOE) from the ministry and, more importantly, through the Research Performing Organisations' in-kind support.

Currently, a particularly relevant project is funded in the framework of PNRR – Recovery and Resilience Plan (Next Generation EU, Miss. 4, Comp. 2), with a substantial investment. The project is named ITINERIS (Italian Integrated Environmental Research Infrastructures System).

ITINERIS aims to build the Italian Hub of Research Infrastructures in the environmental scientific domain. It shall support the observation and study of environmental processes in the atmosphere, marine domain, terrestrial biosphere, and geosphere. Moreover, ITINERIS aims to design and implement methodologies, standards and technological resources to favour access to multidisciplinary services and data. Part of the project activities is meant to promote, facilitate and support harmonized access to services and resources of the participating RIs. ITINERIS, in collaboration with entire ACTRIS, is experimenting with an access programme to test national-co-funded access, which, along with EU-funded access and access possibly financed by other sources, could become a component of the sustainability of RIs' access programmes currently studied in the frame of various ongoing projects.

Users of ACTRIS

Italian user communities are primarily composed of a large number of researchers working on atmospheric research, weather forecasting modelling, climate modelling, modelling of the atmospheric environment, satellite calibration and validation programmes, air quality monitoring, and educational/outreach activities. More than 350 users from this community access ACTRIS Italy's resources each year. The policymakers representing users for ACTRIS are primarily from national governance in its various forms: the Ministry of University and Research, the Ministry of Environment, the National Agency of Aerospace, the regional agencies for environmental monitoring and so on. This user community is more interested in the information content of ACTRIS data that can be used for decision-making or regulatory support. The industrial sector, especially SMEs, represents a user community that can benefit from data and also from access to knowledge and facilities. The linkage with this community is expected to trigger the value chain from research to innovation. More than 155 accesses per year come from different types of users involved in education.

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DEL SALENTO

ACTRIS-The Netherlands

National Contact Person:

Arnoud Apituley

Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI)

Membership status in the ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly:

Member

Nominated delegate:

- Arnoud Apituley

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS:

- Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management
- Ministry of Education, Culture and Science
- Ministry of Economic Affairs
- The Dutch Research Council (NWO)

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium:

- Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI)
- Delft University of Technology (TU-Delft)
- Netherlands Organisation for applied scientific research (TNO)
- Wageningen University and Research (WUR)
- Utrecht University – Institute for Marine and Atmospheric Research (IMAU)
- Free University (VU), Amsterdam
- University of Groningen (RUG)
- National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM)

MEMBER

Highlights

50 years of Cabauw observations

The Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI) research station Cabauw was commissioned more than 50 years ago, which was celebrated in September 2024. The station in the municipality of Lopik consists of a measuring mast 213 meters high and a measuring field around the mast. Since 1972, Cabauw has been used for meteorological measurements in the boundary layer. In the last 50 years, Cabauw has grown into one of the world's most important locations for atmospheric research.

Atmospheric research

The data from the mast from specialized measuring equipment have led to knowledge breakthroughs in the field of boundary layer meteorology, for example how heat exchange between the atmosphere and the Earth's surface works. This has been of great importance for the development of weather and climate models and the understanding of the distribution of air pollution.

Over the years, the measurement programme has been expanded, in collaboration with other knowledge institutes and universities, and the atmosphere is mapped in detail up to a high altitude (15 km). Data from the station can be used to answer scientific and policy questions of today and the future, in the field of climate change, air quality, the energy transition and biodiversity. The station also contributes to providing early warnings for extreme weather.

The Cabauw station is part of the national partnership Ruisdael Observatory and contributes to ACTRIS ERIC and ICOS ERIC.

Advancing Our Understanding of Air Pollution through CINDI-3

In 2024, the third Cabauw Intercomparison of UV-Vis DOAS Instruments (CINDI-3) campaign took place in Cabauw as part of the ACTRIS topical centre for trace gas remote sensing. This international measurement campaign is the largest of its kind in the world.

Satellite validation

Once the instruments have been thoroughly characterised during CINDI-3, they will return to their respective home countries across the globe where they will play a pivotal role in satellite validation for atmospheric composition. Satellite missions specifically addressed are the European Sentinel-5p/TROPOMI and the soon-to-be-launched Sentinel-5 and Sentinel-4, as well as the Korean GEMS satellite and the US TEMPO missions. This signifies the European and global reach of ACTRIS activities.

MAXDOAS and Pandora instruments located near the Cabauw meteorological tower during CINDI-3.

Contribution to the ACTRIS Central Facilities

Central Facility (CF)	CF Unit name	CF Unit description	CF Unit hosting institution
Centre for Cloud Remote Sensing (CCRES)	CCRES-NL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of Doppler Cloud • Radar calibration procedures • Development of quality control package for Doppler Cloud Radars • Training of users, organization of workshops • Test of new instruments 	Delft University of Technology and Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute
Centre for Reactive trace Gases Remote Sensing (CREGARS)	CREGARS-UUVIS-NL	UVVIS intercomparison support at Cabauw site: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of ancillary observations • Instrument expertise • Meteorological and model • Validation support • Contributions to common TC activities 	Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute

ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
Cabauw	Observational Platform	51.971°N 4.927°E -0.7 m a.s.l.	X		X	X	X	X

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

The national roadmap for the large-scale research infrastructure project Ruisdael Observatory includes ACTRIS-NL and ICOS-NL activities.

 www.ruisdael-observatory.nl

Social media: [LinkedIn](#) (Ruisdael Observatory), [X](#) (@RuisdaelObserv)

Funding for ACTRIS

The Ruisdael Observatory project (2018-2027), funded by NWO, is part of the national roadmap of large-scale research infrastructures and is linked to ACTRIS ERIC and ICOS ERIC. The project includes investment in and installation of infrastructure. The NWO funding is matched with cash and in-kind contributions from the project partners.

For 2024-2029 the Dutch government supports the Cabauw tasks in ACTRIS ERIC and ICOS ERIC executed by KNMI and TNO.

Users of ACTRIS

- The users of the ACTRIS-NL facilities in Cabauw are the partners in Ruisdael Observatory, other national and international research institutes and private companies. The Cabauw site participates in the ATMO-ACCESS Trans-National Access program (2021-2025) and has an access policy for visitors that cannot apply in the framework of ACTRIS. Several long-term collaborations exist with private companies at the site.
- For non-remote and virtual access, all measurements are publicly available and have been used by scientists, policymakers and the general public since the start of the observations at Cabauw in 1972. The Cabauw data are well-known in the research community for its use in Numerical Weather Prediction model validation. As of December 2018, the CESAR database has 1731 unique users.
- A particular use of the Cabauw site is for (large scale) field campaigns that have been conducted every one to two years for various subjects, including clouds and radiation research, air quality studies, application of satellite data and satellite validation.

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ACTRIS-Norway

National Contact Person:
Valentin Duflot
 NILU

Membership status in the ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly:
 Member

Nominated delegate:

- Odd Ivar Eriksen

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS:

- Research Council of Norway
- NILU
- Norwegian Environment Agency
- Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium:

- NILU
- Norwegian Meteorological Institute
- CICERO

MEMBER

Highlights

Norway contributes strongly to ACTRIS; NILU leads the ACTRIS Data Centre for the entire infrastructure, and the Norwegian observatories (Zeppelin, Birkenes and Trollhaugen) are taking part in the labelling process as ACTRIS National Facilities. Also, The Birkenes National Facility received the initial acceptance for Aerosol In Situ measurements in January 2023.

The ACTRIS-Norway project started on 1 August 2022, with funding from the Research Council of Norway's "National Initiative for Research Infrastructure". The main objective of ACTRIS-Norway is the implementation of the ACTRIS Data Centre, in accordance with the plans and requirements outlined within ACTRIS ERIC. ACTRIS-Norway makes the sharing of climate and air pollution data easier and more user-friendly, while at the same time increasing data quality. ACTRIS-Norway also makes ACTRIS services and data more accessible to researchers worldwide. Furthermore, ACTRIS-Norway has developed and implemented a new ACTRIS data portal, which is the gateway to all ACTRIS data and data products. In collaboration with ACTRIS-Norway's partners, the Norwegian Meteorological Institute and CICERO, several combined data products are also being developed.

On September 4th, 2024, the beta version of ACTRIS brand new data portal was launched. The ACTRIS portal allows to explore FAIR data for approximately 1100 atmospheric variables for particles, clouds and trace gases measured at around 700 monitoring stations worldwide. This data portal is the result of a long and close collaboration between more than 30 dedicated researchers and system developers from eight leading research organisations in Norway, France, Italy, Finland and Spain.

Contribution to the ACTRIS Central Facilities

Central Facility (CF)	CF Unit name	CF Unit description	CF Unit hosting institution
Data Centre (DC)	Data Discovery, Virtual Access and Services (DVAS)	The ACTRIS Data Discovery, Virtual Access and Services unit (DVAS) is responsible for organising access to measurement data from the topic data centre units, and documentation of procedures as support to observational and exploratory NFs. The ACTRIS DVAS unit offer access to elaborated aerosol, cloud and trace gas data products, issued of advanced multi-instrument synergistic algorithms, long term reanalysis, modelling and satellite data and sources.	Norwegian Institute for Air Research (NILU)
Data Centre (DC)	In situ data centre unit (In Situ)	The In Situ data centre unit provides data curation service for aerosol, cloud and trace gas in situ data, as well as archiving of this data using the EBAS database. This comprises tools for harmonized data submission and meta data templates, inclusion of data and meta data in the data base, documenting (meta)data traceability and provenance, harmonization and data versioning, quality control, archiving, documentation, data identification, and data provision. Training and online tools for QA/QC are offered. The activity enables RRT and NRT data collection, compilation and delivery, and provides tutorial activities.	Norwegian Institute for Air Research (NILU)

ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
Birkenes	Observational Platform	58.388°N 8.252°E 219 m a.s.l.	X					
Trollhaugen	Observational Platform	72.012°S 2.535°E 1553 m a.s.l.	X		X			
Zeppelin*	Observational Platform	78.907°N 11.889°E 475 m a.s.l.	X		X			

*Operation of Zeppelin is in collaboration with Stockholm University on aerosol in situ, and Stockholm University will add the component Cloud in situ to Zeppelin National Facility.

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

ACTRIS is on the national roadmap in Norway with strong support for the ACTRIS Data Centre.

 <https://actris.no>

Social media: [LinkedIn](#) (NILU), [Facebook](#) (NILU), [Instagram](#) (@nilu.no)

Funding for ACTRIS

ACTRIS-Norway is funded by the Research Council of Norway until 2027.

The Norwegian ACTRIS measurements are primarily associated with Norway's obligation to UNECE (United Nations Economic Commission for Europe), CLTRAP (Convention on Long-range Transboundary Air Pollution), and EMEP (European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme). The costs associated with the ACTRIS National Facilities are part of the national monitoring programme and ministry support for observatory infrastructures. This also includes observations of climate gases, total ozone, UV, and contaminants. It is cost-efficient (and scientifically beneficial) to co-locate monitoring.

Users of ACTRIS

- Norwegian Users of the new ACTRIS data portal – ca 15 per month
- Users of Norwegian ACTRIS data - 142

ACTRIS-Poland

National Contact Persons:

Aleksander Pietruczuk

Institute of Geophysics Polish Academy of Sciences

Iwona Stachlewska

University of Warsaw, Faculty of Physics, Institute of Geophysics

Membership status in the ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly

Member

Nominated delegates:

- Michał Rybiński
- Iwona Stachlewska

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS

- Ministry of Science and Higher Education Republic of Poland

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium

- Institute of Geophysics Polish Academy of Sciences
- Institute of Environmental Engineering Polish Academy of Sciences
- Institute of Meteorology and Water Management National Research Institute
- University of Warsaw
- University of Wrocław
- University of Silesia in Katowice
- Poznan University of Life Sciences
- Warsaw University of Technology

MEMBER

Highlights

Three new lidars and cloud radar supporting ACTRIS-Poland

ACTRIS-PL Mobile Lab (US), as well as Wrocław (UWr) and Strzyżów (UW) NFs, are now equipped with new Mie-Raman lidar systems – one eye-safe scanning lidar and two multiwavelength lidars, respectively. What is more, Rzecin (PULS) National Facility equipment is enriched with a new cloud radar. This is a great improvement for the whole ACTRIS-PL consortium, widening the scientific expertise within aerosol and cloud remote sensing.

Dynamic development of cooperation with the Private Sector

ACTRIS-PL experiences a very dynamic development of cooperation with the private sector. The purchase of new aerosol & cloud remote sensing instruments opened collaborations with Raymetrics (GR) and BOWEN (FR). This allowed for the optimization of cloud radar and the testing of different lidars in new environments such as mountains, city, and industrial. Moreover, new solutions developed by the companies were tested extensively by ACTRIS-PL experts. Dedicated measuring campaigns were conducted on request of the private sector in the framework of the ATMO-ACCESS TNA projects: "AGLP" (Licel, DE), "AQUE" (GRASP EARTH, FR), "ETTLA" (Eventech, LV), "MOB-DAISY" (Raymetrics, GR).

All Polish Observational Platforms stepped into labelling

Belsk: submitted an initial application for the ARS component;
Racibórz: AIS component is in initial acceptance (step 1a, 2024);
Rzecin: CRS initial application was submitted. Data are being provided to the CLOUDNET-ACTRIS data portal.
Strzyżów: submitted an initial application for ARS component;
Warsaw: ARS components have been granted for performance evaluation (step 1b, 2023), while the initial application was submitted for CRS. Data are being provided to the EARLINET-ACTRIS and CLOUDNET-ACTRIS data portals.
Wrocław: AIS component is in initial acceptance (step 1a, 2024), while the initial application was submitted for ARS.

In the future, it is considered to expand the Warsaw capabilities with the AIS component with the cooperation of WUT and UW.

Polish Stakeholders Meeting

At the Faculty of Physics of the University of Warsaw, the RI-URBANS Polish Stakeholder Meeting took place on 23rd February 2023. The meeting gathered Polish Stakeholder representatives from 23 institutions (31 individuals). In addition, 6 representatives of the RI-URBANS (2021-2025) and the ATMO-ACCESS (2021-2025) projects have participated online. All members of the ACTRIS-PL consortium were present.

The discussion addressed the topic of a possible joint strategy development in view of the Revision of the EU Ambient Air Quality Directive, including the context of the monitoring programme of the Polish Chief Inspectorate of Environmental Protection (CIEP) and activities of the Institute of Environmental Protection (IEP-NRI).

ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
ACTRIS-Poland Mobile LAB	Mobile Platform	Mobile				X		
Belsk	Observational Platform	51.836°N 20.789°E 173 m a.s.l.	X			X		
Racibórz	Observational Platform	50.084°N 18.192°E 215 m a.s.l.	X			X		
Rzecin	Observational Platform	52.759°N 16.31°E 59 m a.s.l.				X	X	
Strzyżów	Observational Platform	49.879°N 21.861°E 444 m a.s.l.				X		
Warsaw	Observational Platform	52.211°N 20.983°E 112 m a.s.l.				X	X	
Wrocław	Observational Platform	51.114°N 17.035°E 120 m a.s.l.	X			X		

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

ACTRIS-PL is a national consortium consisting of Research Performing Organizations. ACTRIS-PL is a strategic national infrastructure contributing to an international project included in the ESFRI “road map”, and is a part of the Polish Map of Research infrastructures (update January 2020).

All of the ACTRIS-PL stations stepped into the labelling process.

Funding for ACTRIS

Operational costs of ACTRIS-PL in years 2024 - 2028 are financed by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education, Republic of Poland program “Support for the participation of Polish research teams in international research infrastructure projects”.

The development of ACTRIS-PL infrastructure (investment in National Facilities), was supported by The Smart Growth Operational Programme (POIR), excluding the Mazovia region.

In the Mazovia region, Warsaw (UW) National Facility received funding from National Science Center Poland (NCN) grants: joint DAINA-2 Lithuanian-Polish research project “Importance of long-range transport of BIOmass burning emissions to local Smog events in Urban Environments (BIOSURE)” and joint Weave-UNISONO Austrian-Polish research project “Synergetic aerosol remote sensing of Pandora within ACTRIS” (Aeropan).

ACTRIS-PL participate in several international EC grants: ATMO-ACCESS (2021-2025), RI-URBANS (2021-2025), and IRISCC (2024-2028).

Users of ACTRIS

- ACTRIS Poland serves a broad user community, including key national institutions such as the Institute of Environmental Protection – National Research Institute (IEP-NRI) and the Chief Inspectorate of Environmental Protection (CIEP).
- It collaborates with leading research organizations, including ECMWF-CAMS, ESA-ESRIN, ESA-ESTEC, VITO NV, and the National Institute for Space Research in Brazil.
- The private sector also benefits from ACTRIS Poland's expertise, with partnerships involving companies such as Raymetrics (Greece), Eventech Ltd. (Latvia), Licel GmbH (Germany), Nebo Devices Ltd. (Hong Kong), GRASP EARTH (France), BOWEN (France), and BJE Environmental Optics (USA).
- Additionally, ACTRIS Poland actively supports academic development, contributing to the training of students and researchers, with achievements including two habilitations, 13 PhD theses, and 11 MSc theses.

ACTRIS-Romania

National Contact Person:
Doina Nicolae

National Institute of R&D for Optoelectronics

Membership status in the ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly:

Founding Member

Nominated delegates:

- Viorel Vulturescu
- Beatrice Păduroiu

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS:

- Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitalization

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium:

- National Institute of Research and Development for Optoelectronics (INOE)
- Babeş-Bolyai University (UBB)
- "Dunarea de Jos" University of Galati (DJUG)
- Alexandru Ioan Cuza University
- National Institute for Aerospace Research Elie Carafoli (INCAS)
- Alexandru Ioan Cuza University (UAIC)

MEMBER

Highlights

Inauguration of ACTRIS-UBB new observation facility

The Babeş-Bolyai University launched the ACTRIS-UBB Platform on October 21, dedicated to pan-European research on atmospheric composition and climate change.

The [ACTRIS-UBB Platform](#) thus becomes a national facility of the pan-European ACTRIS research infrastructure and an object of interest to the ground-based observing segment of the European Space Agency's Earth observation program.

Three Romanian Observational Facilities have been granted the initial acceptance for five components:

RADO-Bucharest: The National Facility (Observational Platform) is fully operational. All 3 components (AIS, ARS, CRS) have been granted the initial acceptance in 2023. All are submitting data to the ACTRIS data portal.

RADO-Cluj: The National Facility (Observational Platform) is partially operational. The ARS component is fully operational and has been granted the initial acceptance in 2023.

RADO-Galati: The National Facility (Observational Platform) is fully operational. The CRS component has been granted the initial acceptance in 2023 and is submitting data to the ACTRIS data portal.

Visit of the NASA Administrator at the ACTRIS-INOE observation facility

The National Institute for Research and Development in Optoelectronics – INOE 2000 hosted a high-level delegation from the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), the United States Embassy, and the Romanian Space Agency (ROSA) on October 18, 2024.

An important aspect discussed during the visit was INOE's involvement in international atmospheric monitoring networks and projects, such as ACTRIS. During the visit, the delegation had the opportunity to explore the aerosol in situ, aerosol remote sensing and cloud remote sensing laboratories.

The delegation showed a particular interest in INOE's activities related to the validation of satellite products, an essential field for ensuring the quality and accuracy of data obtained from satellites.

Recently, ACTRIS began implementing a joint project with partners from the USA: CARGO-ACT (Cooperation and Agreements enhancing Global interoperability for Aerosol, Cloud and Trace gas research infrastructures).

CARGO-ACT (2024-2027), which involves ACTRIS and three U.S. agencies (ARM User Facility, NASA's MPLNET, and NOAA's GML), represents a first step towards creating a global research infrastructure.

CARS-AHL-INOE coordinates the lidar QA/QC for the EarthCARE Cal/Val pilot (ATMO-ACCESS)

The goal of this pilot project is to organize fast delivery of correlative datasets from a ground-based network for validation of the aerosol and cloud data products of EarthCARE, including preparation, coordination, development and implementation of common tools, production of harmonized metadata, development of tailored ACTRIS products, and thorough quality monitoring and intercalibration.

The main activities are: preparation for the tools and plans for validation; preparation for data acquisition and rapid processing; pre-launch network rehearsal campaign with fast data delivery; post-launch validation with Near Real Time (NRT) data delivery during commissioning phase; Intercalibration with other networks and ESA's reference instruments.

Contribution to the ACTRIS Central Facilities

Central Facility (CF)	CF Unit name	CF Unit description	CF Unit hosting institution
Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing (CARS)	AHL-INOE	Management of the CF, QA/QC of lidar measurements, development of procedures and tools for lidar QA/QC, associated training and consultancy, link with EARLINET, ESA and EUMETSAT	National Institute of Research and Development for Optoelectronics

ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
ATMOSLAB	Mobile Platform	Mobile	X	X		X		
CERNESIM	Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	47.166°N 27.566°E 66 m a.s.l.	X		X			
RADO-Bucharest	Observational Platform	44.348°N 26.029°E 93 m a.s.l.	X			X	X	
RADO-Cluj	Observational Platform	46.766°N 23.583°E 352 m a.s.l.				X	X	
RADO-Galati	Observational Platform	45.438°N 28.056°E 35 m a.s.l.					X	
RADO-Iasi	Observational Platform	47.166°N 27.566°E 66 m a.s.l.				X		

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

The institutions are collaboratively organized in the ACTRIS-RO consortium and have signed a Memorandum of Understanding back in 2015 for the implementation of ACTRIS activities. ACTRIS-RO was included in the national roadmap for research infrastructures already in 2017, and re-confirmed in 2021.

 <https://actris.ro>

Social media: [X \(@ACTRIS_RO\)](#)

Funding for ACTRIS

Although a national roadmap for RIs exists in Romania, no direct funding is provided. All RIs on the national roadmap are eligible to apply to specific competitive calls, as part of programs dedicated to research infrastructures. However, funding is not guaranteed. If successful, a contract is signed with the funding agency for specific activities indicated in the call, which may combine implementation and operation activities, partially funded, but also research activities. The consortium has attracted funding over the years through competitive programs, managing the development of top laboratories, as well as attracting national and international specialists.

Users of ACTRIS

- ACTRIS-Romania serves a diverse community of users across various sectors. The University of Bucharest engages approximately 70 students and academic staff, while the Politehnica University of Timișoara involves around 30 individuals in research and education.
- The National Meteorological Administration and the Romanian Air Traffic Services Administration each have about 10 researchers and meteorologists utilizing ACTRIS resources. "Politehnica" University of Bucharest contributes an additional 50 students and academics.
- The National Institute for Earth Physics includes approximately 5 researchers in its activities, and "Gheorghe Asachi" Technical University of Iași involves around 20 students and academic personnel. Additionally, S.C. INOESY S.R.L. employs about 3 engineers who benefit from ACTRIS services.

ACTRIS-Spain

National Contact Persons:

Amalia Muñoz

Fundación Centro de Estudios Ambientales del Mediterráneo (CEAM)

Carlos Toledano

University of Valladolid

Membership status in the ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly:

Member

Nominated delegate:

- María Vallejo Abascal

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS:

- Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities
- Ministry for the Ecologic Transition and the Demographic Challenge.
- Department of Health, Regional Government of Catalonia
- Ministry of Defence
- Department of Economy and Knowledge, Regional Government of Andalusia
- Department of Economy, Industry, Commerce and Knowledge, Regional Government of the Canary Islands
- Department of Education, Regional Government of Castilla y León
- Department of Business and Labour, Regional Government of Catalonia
- Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, Regional Government of Catalonia
- Department of Health, Regional Government of Catalonia
- Department of Environment, Water Infrastructure and Territory, Regional Government of Comunitat Valenciana

- Department of Education and Research, Regional Government of Madrid
- Agencia Estatal de Meteorología (AEMET)
- Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC)
- Barcelona Supercomputing Center – Centro Nacional de Supercomputación (BSC)
- Instituto Interuniversitario de Investigación del Sistema Tierra en Andalucía – Universidad de Granada (IISTA-UGR)
- Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas (CIEMAT)
- Fundación de la Comunitat Valenciana Centro de Estudios Ambientales del Mediterráneo (CEAM)
- Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial (INTA)
- Universidad Miguel Hernández (UMH)
- Universidad de Valladolid (UVA)
- Universitat de València (UV)
- Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium:

- Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC)
- Agencia Estatal de Meteorología (AEMET)
- Barcelona Supercomputing Center – Centro Nacional de Supercomputación (BSC)
- Instituto Interuniversitario de Investigación del Sistema Tierra en Andalucía – Universidad de Granada (IISTA-UGR)
- Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas (CIEMAT)
- Fundación de la Comunitat Valenciana Centro de Estudios Ambientales del Mediterráneo (CEAM)
- Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial (INTA)
- Universidad Miguel Hernández (UMH)
- Universidad de Valladolid (UVA)
- Universitat de València (UV)
- Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)

Highlights

In 2024, ACTRIS-Spain achieved significant milestones in atmospheric research and education. Prof. Constantino Muñoz from UPC delivered a series of lectures on "Lidar Techniques for Atmospheric Sounding" at the Maïdo Observatory Summer School, held at Université de La Réunion from November 18 to 22. Prof. Adolfo Comerón, also from UPC, presented "Spain's Contribution to the European Research Infrastructure Consortium ACTRIS ERIC" during the special session on Remote Sensing and Environmental Sensors at the Spanish National Congress on Environment 2024 ([CONAMA 2024](#)) on December 2. PhD student Daniel Camilo Fortunato Dos Santos Oliveira conducted a seminar on Multi-Sensor Aerosol Inversions from November 25 to 27 at Université de La Réunion.

ESAt-El Arenosillo initiated a system for the continuous operation of scattering enhancement factors based on nephelometric techniques, successfully obtaining the first year of data. Throughout 2024, IDAEA CSIC implemented a new traffic supersite in Barcelona, collaborating with the Air Quality Department of Catalonia and the Barcelona Public Health Agency (ASPB). Aerosol in situ measurements adhered to ACTRIS and RI-URBANS (2021-2025) recommendations.

The "AGORA: Training School on Characterization of Atmospheric Aerosol Using In Situ and Remote Sensing Techniques" (2nd edition) was organized from June 6 to 21 at the Global Atmosphere Observatory in Andalusia (Granada, Spain). This hybrid-format school provided fundamental knowledge in advanced techniques for measuring atmospheric aerosol properties, including in situ instrumentation, remote sensing, and laboratory-based methods.

Several Transnational Access (TNA) campaigns were conducted at the EUPHORE simulation chamber, funded by the ATMO-ACCESS project (2021-2025):

ISAMO: Studied iron salt aerosols' methane oxidation to understand the impact of dust on atmospheric chlorine and methane budgets (January and September 2024).

MIND-BB: Investigated atmospheric physical and chemical processes of biomass burning from various domestic heating devices, assessing their impact on human lung cells (November 2024).

These initiatives underscore ACTRIS-Spain's commitment to advancing atmospheric research and fostering international collaboration.

Contribution to the ACTRIS Central Facilities

Central Facility (CF)	CF Unit name	CF Unit description	CF Unit hosting institution
Data Centre (DC)	Data Discovery, virtual Access and Services Unit (DVAS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Data production of selected Level 3 data and synergy data products	Barcelona Supercomputing Center – Centro Nacional de Supercomputación
Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing (CARS)	ASP-AEMET	<ul style="list-style-type: none">Calibrating reference sun-photometer required by CNRS and UVAPrimary link to WMO-GAW reference AOD network (traceability)Testing of new technics and methodologies for photometry measurements.Development of synergy photometer/lidar/ceilometer methodologies	State Meteorological Agency of Spain (AEMET), Izaña Atmospheric Research Center

Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing (CARS)	CARS-ASP-UVA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance and calibration transfer from reference instrument automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers to field instrument • NASA radiance traceability with CARS • Update of photometer monitoring tools, such as CAELIS (www.caelis.uva.es) • Submission of photometer level 1 data to ACTRIS DC • Update ACTRIS-DC processing software and system for ASP level 2/3 data production 	University of Valladolid, Group of Atmospheric Optics
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ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
Izaña Atmospheric Observatory	Observational Platform	28.3°N 16.5°W 2370 m a.s.l.	X					
Madrid	Observational Platform	40.456°N 3.726°W 700 m a.s.l.	X			X		
Barcelona	Observational Platform	41.387°N 2.116°E 115 m a.s.l.	X			X		
Montserrat	Observational Platform	41.779°N 2.358°E 720 m a.s.l.	X					
Montsec	Observational Platform	42.052°N 0.7294°E 1600 m a.s.l.	X					
Agora	Observational Platform	37.2°N 3.6°W 680 m a.s.l.	X			X	X	
ESAt - El Arenosillo	Observational Platform	37.1°N 6.7°W 40 m a.s.l.	X					
EUropean PHOto-Reactor (EUPHORE, CEAM)	Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	39.5°N 0.5°W 70 m a.s.l.	X		X			

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

ACTRIS-Spain is currently organized under a Joint Research Unit (JRU) signed by 11 RPOs, namely:

- Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC)
- Agencia Estatal de Meteorología (AEMET)
- Barcelona Supercomputer Center - Centro Nacional de Supercomputación (BSC)
- Instituto Interuniversitario de Investigación del Sistema Tierra en Andalucía. Universidad de Granada (IISTA-UGR)
- Centro de Investigaciones Energéticas, Medioambientales y Tecnológicas (CIEMAT)
- Fundación de la Comunitat Valenciana Centro de Estudios Ambientales del
- Mediterráneo (CEAM)
- Instituto Nacional de Técnica Aeroespacial (INTA)
- Universidad Miguel Hernández (UMH)
- Universidad de Valladolid (UVA)
- Universitat de València (UV)
- Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC)

The Spanish National Research Infrastructure Roadmap does not exist at present.

 <https://www.actris.es/en>

Social media: [Instagram](#) (@actrispain)

Funding for ACTRIS

ACTRIS-Spain has primarily been funded through public grants at national and regional levels, contributions from Research Performing Organizations, mainly in-kind, and additional support from European Framework Programme projects. The membership fee is financed by the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation, and Universities.

Users of ACTRIS

The number of people potentially using ACTRIS products in Spain is estimated to be 300 in the academic domain and 700 in the rest of the fields, including industries, meteorological and environmental agencies, health agencies and policymakers at the national, regional and local levels.

The following types of ACTRIS users have been identified in Spain:

By application of ACTRIS products:

- Climate modelling
- Atmospheric environment modelling and forecast
- Ecological research and monitoring
- Health studies and epidemiology
- Energy (solar energy)

By activity domain:

- Academic research
- Meteorological agencies
- Environmental ministries and agencies at national and regional levels
- Natural resources ministries and agencies at national and regional levels
- Health agencies
- Industrial users, including companies of a large span of sizes and activities

Present known users include:

- Climate modelling, and atmospheric environment modelling and forecast research groups at Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, and Universidad de Extremadura, Universidad de Copenhagen.
- Several departments at the Meteorological Agency of Spain (AEMET).
- The environmental agency of the Castilla y León Regional Government.
- General Directorate of Environmental Quality and Climate Change, from the Department of Climate Action, Food and Rural Agenda, Regional Government of Catalonia
- A health research and epidemiology group at the Institute of Biomedical Studies Instituto de Salud Carlos III.
- ISGlobal - Barcelona Institute for Global Health - ISGLOBAL
- Private Sector: Companies developing scientific instruments in the atmospheric domain
- International researchers from the UK, Denmark, Germany, etc
- National Agencies for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development from Other Countries

It is reasonably considered that future users can include councils of major Spanish cities, departments with responsibilities in the environment, Air quality network stations' managers, public health, agriculture and food at national and regional levels (besides those already mentioned), as well private companies, especially, but not exclusively, in the energy sector (electricity, gas, oil, etc.).

Some international communities, such as those reached by the WMO's Sand and Dust Storm Warning Advisory and Assessment System (SDS-WAS) Regional Northern Africa-Middle East-Europe (NA-ME-E) Regional Center, under the responsibility of AEMET and BSC, are also potential users of ACTRIS products with high probability.

ACTRIS-Sweden

National Contact Person:

Erik Swietlicki

Lund University

Membership status in the ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly:

Member

Nominated delegates:

- Sara Moa
- Ulf Jonsell

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS:

- Swedish Research Council
- Swedish Environment Protection Agency
- Lund University
- Stockholm University
- Gothenburg University
- Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU)
- Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI)
- Uppsala University
- Swedish private foundations

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium:

- Lund University, Erik Swietlicki
- Stockholm University, Radovan Krejci
- Gothenburg University, Mattias Hallquist
- Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Hjalmar Laudon
- Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute SMHI, Salomon Eliasson
- Uppsala University, Anna Rutgersson

Highlights

The ACTRIS-related activities continued uninterrupted at the stations that were established already prior to the start of ACTRIS Sweden in 2022; Hyltemossa and Norunda in Sweden and Zeppelin on Svalbard. The two new Swedish ACTRIS stations at Östergarnsholm and Svartberget and the Mobile Exploratory AIS-RTGIS Platform will be made operational in 2025-2026. The AIS labelling of ACTRIS Sweden stations started with the Zeppelin station on Svalbard in 2023, Hyltemossa in 2024 and Norunda in 2025. CiGas experts will commence audits for RTGIS in 2025.

The forest around the ACTRIS-ICOS station at Norunda was clear-cut during 2022-2023, which opened for new scientific studies and comparisons of concentrations and land-atmosphere fluxes for the periods before and after the clear-cutting.

ACTRIS-Sweden will move from an implementation and build-up phase during 2022-2026 to a mainly operational phase 2027-2030, focusing on consolidating ACTRIS Sweden as a national research infrastructure in the climate and environmental area.

ACTRIS-Sweden has investigated synergies with ICOS Sweden and SITES, a Swedish Infrastructure for Ecosystem Science similar to European eLTER. Our three RIs have agreed on several concrete short-term aims as well as a long-term vision for maximizing scientific value in Earth system sciences and for organizational and economic efficiency.

ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
Exploratory Platform SMHI	Mobile Platform	Mobile					X	
Exploratory Platform UG	Mobile Platform	Mobile, under construction, operational 2026	X		X			
Hyltemossa	Observational Platform	56.098°N 13.419°E 115 m a.s.l.	X		X			
Norunda	Observational Platform	60.083°N 17.483°E 46 m a.s.l.	X		X			
Östergarnsholm	Observational Platform	57.430°N 18.984°E -	X					
Svartberget	Observational Platform	64.250°N 19.767°E 270 m a.s.l.	X		X			
Zeppelin	Observational Platform	78.908°N 11.881°E 474 m a.s.l.	X	X				

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

Since 2017, ACTRIS-Sweden has been on the Swedish Research Infrastructure Roadmap in the highest Category A1. This paved the way for ACTRIS-Sweden to be established in 2022 as a national research infrastructure with financial support from the Swedish Research Council. In turn, this enabled Sweden to become one of the founding members of ACTRIS ERIC in 2023.

The ACTRIS-Sweden observations are made along a 3000 km south-north gradient and hence also a high-to-low gradient in anthropogenic pollution and boreal-to-polar climate. It is expected that ACTRIS-Sweden – with its co-localization with ICOS Sweden providing long-term observations on long-lived greenhouse gases, their variability, sources and sinks – will have a critical impact on enhancing excellence in Earth system observations and research by providing information and knowledge for the development of sustainable solutions to societal needs.

On request from the Swedish Research Council, extensive discussions have taken place between ACTRIS Sweden, ICOS Sweden and SITES (Swedish Infrastructure for Ecosystem Science). SITES is a Swedish national research infrastructure similar to European eLTER in the ESFRI environment and climate domain. These discussions resulted in a strategic plan for enhanced cooperation between ACTRIS-Sweden, ICOS Sweden and SITES for maximizing scientific value and organizational and economic efficiency.

Funding for ACTRIS

The Swedish Research Council granted 62.9 MSEK in funding to the new national research infrastructure ACTRIS Sweden for the initial 5-year implementation period 2022-2026. Participating Research Performing Organisations also contribute with 69.3 MSEK in co-funding. On top of this, the Swedish Research Council pays the ERIC membership fee (6.5 MSEK for 2022-2026). Major investments are made during 2022-2026 for the procurement of scientific instrumentation (39.1 MSEK) and the establishment of two new Observational Platforms (Svartberget, Östergarnsholm) and a Mobile Exploratory AIS-RTGIS Platform.

ACTRIS Sweden will then move from an implementation and build-up phase during 2022-2026 to a mainly operational phase 2027-2030. The focus will be on the consolidation of ACTRIS-Sweden as a national research infrastructure in the climate and environmental area, co-located with ICOS stations and collaborating also with SITES.

Users of ACTRIS

At the Universities in Lund, Stockholm and Gothenburg and at SMHI, several of the researchers in these areas of science are involved in the Strategic Research Areas ([SRA](#)) MERGE; Bolin Centre for Climate Research ([BBCC](#)) and Biodiversity and Ecosystem services in a Changing Climate ([BECC](#)). These SRA are developing climate and Earth system models (MERGE, BBCC) with a strong coupling to biodiversity and ecosystem services (BECC).

To these strong research communities, ACTRIS provides data that are used for model development and verification across a wide range of temporal and spatial scales, going from detailed atmospheric chemistry and aerosol dynamics models to Earth system models such as EC-Earth.

In Sweden, several stakeholders and practitioners would benefit from ACTRIS services and data:

Governmental agencies

- Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (air quality and climate)
- Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (climate change and meteorology)
- Swedish Energy Agency (sustainable energy production)
- Swedish Forest Agency (climate change and forest management, forest fires, etc.)
- Swedish Board of Agriculture (climate change and agriculture etc.)
- Swedish Civil Contingencies Agency MSB (climate change, forest fires, etc.)
- LFV Group (air navigation services and volcanoes)
- Swedish Transport Agency (air traffic and volcano plumes, climate change and transport etc.)

Private-sector, research institutes

Selection of Swedish research institutes that would benefit from the ACTRIS RI and data:

- IVL Swedish Environmental Research Institute

- Swedish Geotechnical Institute (SGI)
- Geological Survey of Sweden (SGU)

Political

- Swedish Government and Parliament (basis for decision-making)
- Swedish Ministry of Climate and Enterprise
- Ministry of Education and Research
- Permanent Representation of Sweden to the EU
- Swedish regional authorities and municipalities
- Swedish regional air quality associations

Industry

- Forest sector, wood and paper industry, energy production sector, hydropower, insurance sector, tourism

ACTRIS-Switzerland

National Contact Person:
Martin Gysel-Beer
Paul Scherrer Institute

Membership status in the ACTRIS ERIC General Assembly:
Permanent Observer

Nominated delegate:

- Maarten Lupker

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS:

- State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation SERI
- Federal Office for the Environment FOEN
- Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology MeteoSwiss
- Swiss National Science Foundation

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium:

- Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology (Empa), Dr. Stefan Reimann
- Physikalisch-Meteorologisches Observatorium Davos/World Radiation Center (PMOD/WRC), Dr. Stelios Kazadzis
- Institute for Atmospheric and Climate Science (IAC), ETH Zürich, Dr. Zamin Kanji
- University of Bern, Dr. Axel Murk
- Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology, MeteoSwiss, Dr. Martine Collaud Coen
- Paul Scherrer Institute

PERMANENT OBSERVER

Highlights

ACTRIS-Switzerland operates six ACTRIS facilities, two Central Facility units, one Exploratory Platform and three Observational Platforms, which serve both common and type-specific user groups. Central Facility units have a focus on expert training, ensuring data quality for scientific applications, and method development in collaboration with private companies and national institutes of metrology.

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The Exploratory Platform PACS serves researchers as a user platform for sophisticated process studies as well as for testing advanced instruments for atmospherically relevant samples under controlled conditions. The Observational Platforms are tailored towards providing comprehensive and high-quality data sets for Earth system research in addition to hosting researchers for field experiments.

Contribution to the ACTRIS Central Facilities

Central Facility (CF)	CF Unit name	CF Unit description	CF Unit hosting institution
Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing (CARS)	Automatic Sun/sky/lunar Photometer PMOD-WRC (ASP-PMOD-WRC)	Provision of calibration services and establishing traceability of aerosol optical depth measurements within ACTRIS to the reference scale of the World Meteorological Organization.	Physikalisch-Meteorologisches Observatorium Davos/World Radiation Center
Centre for Reactive Trace Gases In Situ Measurements (CiGas)	CiGas-Empa	Development of an on-line tool (@VOC@, atmospheric VOC assessment tool) for checking the data quality of VOCs before final publication at the database, Preparation of common calibrated VOC-in-air working standards	Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology

ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
Beromuenster	Observational Platform	47.19°N 8.175°E 797 m a.s.l.			X			
Jungfrauoch	Observational Platform	46.547°N 7.985°E 3580 m a.s.l.	X	X	X			
PACS	Atmospheric Simulation Chamber	47.539°N 8.229°E 335 m a.s.l.	X		X			
Payerne	Observational Platform	46.813°N 6.944°E 489 m a.s.l.	X			X	X	

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

ACTRIS entered the Swiss Roadmap for Research Infrastructures in 2019, which enabled the establishment of the national consortium and implementation of the ACTRIS facilities in Switzerland.

 www.actris.ch

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Funding for ACTRIS

Current funding for ACTRIS Switzerland is around 2.5 M€ per year. In 2024, the State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation committed funding for the 2025-2028 period to finalize implementation and transition to operation. ACTRIS Switzerland further relies on financial support from the RPOs, synergies with co-located observation networks, and infrastructure hosting the facilities such as the High Altitude Research Station Jungfrauoch.

Users of ACTRIS

- Several research projects funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation or other funding bodies benefit from the facilities and data and facilities provided by ACTRIS.
- The facilities, data and researchers of ACTRIS Switzerland serve academic education through practical courses, theses, summer schools and training workshops.
- Observational data acquired at the national facilities serve the national and international research community to investigate sources and environmental impacts of short-lived atmospheric constituents and to validate model simulations.
- High-quality measurement data of the central and national facilities serve as a reference for new prototypes from instrument manufacturers.
- ACTRIS researchers are part of many national and international bodies related to aerosols, clouds and trace gases.
- The ACTRIS Switzerland consortium contributes to capacity building through bilateral initiatives and at stations of the Global Atmosphere Watch Program.
- The national facilities regularly host visitors from the general public, governmental and private sectors. In addition, scientific findings are communicated through newspapers.

Project funded by

Federal Office for the Environment FOEN

Federal Department of Home Affairs FDHA
Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology MeteoSwiss

Joint Research Centre

Contact Person:

Jean-Philippe Putaud

Highlights:

The Joint Research Centre (JRC) has been operating the Atmospheric Observatory located on the edge of the Po Valley (45.815 °N, 8.636°E, 219 m asl) for close to 40 years. NO_x concentrations have been measured since then, and non-methane hydrocarbon (NMHC) measurements have been resumed since 2019. Particulate organic and elemental carbon (OC and EC) in PM_{2.5} have been regularly measured since 2002, aerosol particle microphysical and optical properties since 2004, and aerosol vertical profiles since 2006. Currently, the data series from JRC's observatory are amongst the 3-4 longest in Europe. JRC's observatory has been granted the initial acceptance in the labelling process for in situ measurements in 2022. All other measurements are carried out according to ACTRIS recommendations, but the labelling process for trace gas in situ measurements and aerosol remote sensing has not started yet due to a lack of human and financial resources.

Various data sets have been used in several local (3) and continental (21) studies published in peer-review literature during the 10 last years.

The JRC has also developed the thermal protocol for organic and elemental carbon (OC and EC) analyses adopted by the European standard EN16909:2017, recommended by ACTRIS. Under the ACTRIS Topical Centre for Aerosol In Situ Measurements (CAIS-ECAC), it has provided the scientific community with a QA/QC service for the analysis of particulate OC and EC, organizing, running, and analyzing annual inter-laboratory comparisons joined by an increasing number of participants (ca. 14 to 40) since 2007.

JRC's staff has also been giving lectures in ACTRIS aerosol courses each year (since before ACTRIS was born), and support to the National Facilities by providing advice and feedback on request.

JOINT RESEARCH CENTRE

4. ACTRIS-Engaging Countries

ACTRIS-Estonia

National Contact Person:

Steffen M. Noe

Estonian University of Life Science

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS:

- Ministry of Climate
- Ministry of Education and Research
- Estonian Research Council

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium:

- Estonian University of Life Sciences, Institute of Forestry and Engineering
- University of Tartu, Environmental Physics and Tartu Observatory

Highlights

ACTRIS-Estonia has been actively contributing to atmospheric science through various initiatives and achievements. Members of the consortium participated in the 2024 European Aerosol Conference held in Tampere, Finland, presenting their work through oral and poster presentations.

Recent publications include studies utilizing neural networks to assess air pollution using a bioindicator system and the classification of urban air pollution in a large Brazilian city using low-cost sensor systems, both featured in *Frontiers in Big Data*. Additionally, a significant study estimating the methane leak from the Nordstream incident in 2022 was published.

In August, ACTRIS-Estonia organized a Doctoral School on the application of low-cost sensors in forest ecosystems, hosted at the SMEAR Estonia station and the Estonian Experimental and Training Forest Center in Järvelja.

Potential ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
SMEAR Estonia Atmosphere-Ecosystem Supersite	Observational Platform, background site in South-East Estonia	58.277°N 27.308°E 36 m a.s.l.	X		X		X	
Tahkuse	Observational Platform, rural background	58.525°N 24.925°E 24 m a.s.l.	X		X			
Estonian University of Life Sciences	Observational Platform, drone	Mobile			X			

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

All partners are participating in the [Estonian Environmental Observatory](#) consortium. This consortium has a common agreement. During 2024, a renewal of the national roadmap has been conducted and the Estonian Environmental Observatory is part of the new roadmap.

 <https://actris.emu.ee>

Funding for ACTRIS

So far, there is no dedicated funding for ACTRIS Estonia. The only funding sources are linked with the participating scientists and Research Performing Organisations' project-driven funding opportunities.

Users of ACTRIS

ACTRIS-Estonia serves a diverse user base, including approximately 2-3 governmental organisations, 4 educational institutions, 4-5 communal entities, and 3-5 private sector representatives.

REPUBLIC OF ESTONIA
MINISTRY OF CLIMATE

Estonian
Research Council

Eesti Maaülikool
Estonian University of Life Sciences

REPUBLIC OF ESTONIA
MINISTRY OF EDUCATION
AND RESEARCH

ACTRIS-Greece

National Contact Person:

Nikolaos Mihalopoulos

University of Crete and National Observatory of Athens

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS:

- Ministry of Development (General Secretary of Research and Innovation)
- Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)
- University of Crete
- University of Patras
- National observatory of Athens (NOA)
- Foundation for Research and Technology (FORTH)
- National Centre for Scientific Research – Demokritos
- European Investment Bank (EIB)
- Recovery Funds

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium:

- Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)
- University of Crete
- University of Patras
- National observatory of Athens (NOA)
- Foundation for Research and Technology (FORTH)
- National Centre for Scientific Research – Demokritos

Highlights

Aerosol remote sensing data from ACTRIS-Greece National Facilities have been integrated into the QA/QC procedures of major EUMETSAT and ESA missions, including GOME-2, TROPOMI, AEOLUS, and EARTHCARE.

Members of ACTRIS-Greece have been elected to the ACTRIS expert group dedicated to the calibration and validation (CAL/VAL) of satellite atmospheric composition products.

2024 marked significant milestones for in situ aerosol facilities, with Finokalia (FKL) celebrating 33 years and Thissio (NOA) marking 11 years of continuous operation.

Additionally, the Hellenic ACTRIS Center (HAC2) participated as a key component of the [CleanCloud project](#), led by [EPFL](#) in Lausanne.

Since May 2024, work has progressed at the PANGAEA station in Antikythera, with nearly €15 million worth of instrumentation ordered. The PANGAEA infrastructure is expected to become operational by the end of 2025.

Potential ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
Thessaloniki	Observational Platform	40.63°N 22.95°E 50 m a.s.l.				X		
Finokalia	Observational Platform	35.33°N 25.26°E 250 m a.s.l.	X					
Athens NOA	Observational Platform	37.97°N 23.72°E 105 m a.s.l.	X					
Athens DEM	Observational Platform	37.99°N 23.82°E 270 m a.s.l.	X					
PANGEA	Observational Platform	35.86°N 23.30°E 193 m a.s.l.	X			X	X	X
PANGEA	Mobile Platform	Mobile				X		
FORTH-ASC	Ground-based fixed/Chamber	38.29°N 21.78°E 49 m a.s.l.	X					

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

The Greek-ACTRIS consortium is under the umbrella of PANACEA Research infrastructure (see link below). An application was submitted in January 2024 to ensure the finance and operation of the ACTRIS-Greece consortium for the next 5 years. Results are expected in 2025.

 <https://panacea-ri.gr/?lang=en>

Funding for ACTRIS

A proposal to cover ACTRIS-Greece consortium funding is under evaluation. Results are expected within 2025. Funding (mainly the salary of the permanent personnel and part of operational costs) is supported by the relevant Universities and Research Centres.

Users of ACTRIS

- Regions
- Municipalities

ACTRIS-Ireland

National Contact Person:
John Wenger
 University College Cork (UCC)

Ministries and other possible funding organisations supporting ACTRIS

- Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science
- Research Ireland
- Department of Environment, Climate and Communications
- Environmental Protection Agency

Research performing organisations in the national ACTRIS consortium

- University College Cork (UCC)
- University of Galway (UoG)
- Met Éireann

Highlights

The Centre for Research into Atmospheric Chemistry (CRAC) at UCC was a hive of activity in 2024, hosting visitors from several European countries at the Irish Atmospheric Simulation Chamber (IASC) facility.

Dr Maarten Kieft, CEO of [Luper Technologies](#) based in the Netherlands, and PhD student Merve Polat from the National Research Centre for the Working Environment in Denmark, conducted a 3-week programme of simulation chamber experiments on the atmospheric oxidation of benzene and naphthalene to help unravel some of the complex chemistry associated with these important air pollutants. The research will support the development of Luper's Air Shield technology for reducing air pollution from asphalt production plants.

Dr Williams Esteve and Dr Sophie Tomaz, from the French [National Research and Safety Institute](#) for the Prevention of Occupational Accidents and Diseases, carried out some highly novel experiments in the simulation chamber to assess the potential atmospheric processing of fire-retardant coatings on surfaces. The research will be used to assess the potential health implications arising from degradation of fire retardants such as triphenyl phosphate in the workplace and other environments.

The researchers were hosted by the CRAC team led by Prof John Wenger and Prof Andy Ruth. Transnational access to the Centre's unique research facility was supported through the European Union Horizon 2020 project ATMO ACCESS.

Potential ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
Mace Head Atmospheric Research Station (UoG)	Observational Platform, Atlantic coastal site in North-west of Ireland	53.3258°N 9.8994°W 5 m a.s.l.	X		X	X	X	
Irish Atmospheric Simulation Chamber (IASC) Facility (UCC)	Exploratory Platform, large indoor Teflon chamber	51.8930°N 8.4942°W 15 m a.s.l.	X		X			
Valentia Observatory (Met Éireann)	Observational Platform, coastal site in South-west of Ireland	51.9397°N 10.2444°W 9 m a.s.l.	X			X	X	

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

The two main participants (UoG and UCC) have been involved with the ACTRIS community for well over a decade and have participated in all projects carried out to date. However, Ireland does not have a current national research infrastructure roadmap and securing support for involvement in ACTRIS is therefore very challenging. There are no formal procedures to follow and discussions with the relevant government departments and agencies have so far proved to be unproductive. Nevertheless, UCC and UoG remain committed to continued engagement with the Irish government to secure support for establishing ACTRIS-Ireland and joining the ERIC as a full member.

Funding for ACTRIS

The Observational and Exploratory Platforms in UoG and UCC have been developed with funds obtained from national research funding mechanisms. The respective institutions have also supported these research facilities by providing equipment and staff. However, the continued operation of these facilities into the Operational Phase of ACTRIS can only be ensured if the government commits to establish ACTRIS-Ireland and support it with targeted national funding.

Users of ACTRIS

ACTRIS-Ireland serves a diverse range of users, including researchers from various academic institutes across Ireland, as well as state organizations such as the EPA and Met Éireann, which focus on air quality and atmospheric modelling. Local authorities, including city and county councils, also benefit from access to air quality data, while private sector companies—ranging from airlines and scientific instrument developers to air quality sensor manufacturers—rely on ACTRIS resources to support their operations and innovation.

ACTRIS-Portugal

© Daniele Bortoli

National Contact Person:
Daniele Bortoli

CREATE – Center for Sci-Tech Research in Earth
sysTem and Energy – University of Evora

**Ministries and other possible funding
organisations supporting ACTRIS:**

- Technology and Science Foundation (FCT)
- Commissions for Coordination of Regional Development (CCDRs)
- Ministério da Ciência, Tecnologia e Ensino Superior (MCTES)

For all: financial commitment to be confirmed

**Research performing organisations in the
national ACTRIS consortium:**

- University of Evora
- University of Aveiro
- University of Azores
- University of Beira Interior
- LEPABE - Laboratory for Process Engineering, Environment, Biotechnology and Energy - LEPABE University of Porto
- IPMA - Instituto Portugueso do Mar e Atmosfera

Highlights

ACTRIS-Portugal has made significant contributions both nationally and internationally. On the national level, the team actively participated in workshops and conferences to promote the ACTRIS-ERIC infrastructure, advocating for Portugal's legal involvement and encouraging the inclusion of new research-performing institutions, including universities, research centres, and associated laboratories. They also organized both online and in-person meetings to discuss the status of Portuguese research within the ACTRIS framework. Additionally, local observations were leveraged to issue population warnings about Saharan dust intrusions, with findings published in general science journals.

On the international stage, ACTRIS-Portugal has engaged in long-term, coordinated measurement campaigns aimed at evaluating the chemical and physical properties of atmospheric aerosols. They have been involved in the classification of these aerosols and in satellite calibration and validation activities for missions like CALIPSO and EarthCARE. Furthermore, ACTRIS-Portugal has conducted dedicated experiments to study exceptional environmental events, including the COVID-19 pandemic, volcanic eruptions, and wildfire events, contributing valuable data to these global efforts.

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Potential ACTRIS National Facilities – ACTRIS Observational Platforms and Exploratory Platforms

National Facility (NF) name	Description	Coordinates & altitude (m)	Aerosol IS	Cloud IS	RTG IS	Aerosol RS	Cloud RS	RTG RS
EVASO - Évora Atmospheric Sciences Observatory	Observational Platform, background site	38.5678°N 7.9115°W 293 m a.s.l.	X			X	X	X
PMO - Pico Mountain Observatory	Observational Platform, maritime background	38.0478°N 28.4038°W 2225 m a.s.l.				X		
Mobile Station for Air Quality Assessment	Exploratory Platforms	Mobile	X		X			

The status of the national ACTRIS consortium

Since 2009, the University of Evora through the CREATE - Center for Sci-Tec Research in Earth System and Energy - (formerly ICT and CGE) has been the only Portuguese-associated partner of the ACTRIS projects (ACTRIS, ACTRIS2, ACTRIS-PPP). Only in 2015, the Portuguese research institutions started to organize themselves as a consortium and nowadays the Portuguese ACTRIS community is discussing with the decision-makers the setup of the consortium. Following a request from the National Science Foundation (FCT), in 2020 the application for the inclusion of the ACTRIS-Portugal consortium (ACTRIS-PT) in the Infrastructures National Roadmap, has been submitted. Nowadays, no answer from the institutions.

The Portuguese Science Foundation is partially supporting the national ACTRIS activities of the associated partners.

Social media: [X \(@ActrisPt\)](#)

Funding for ACTRIS

Even after some more meetings with the funding authorities, it is not yet possible to quantify the available Portuguese financial support to ACTRIS.

Users of ACTRIS

ACTRIS-Portugal serves a diverse range of stakeholders, including the scientific research community focused on environmental issues and air quality, regional departments responsible for air quality management, the education sector, the transport sector—particularly air traffic—and the health sector.

5. Appendices

ACTRIS Glossary

ACTRIS - The Pan-European distributed Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure which produces high-quality data documenting short-lived atmospheric constituents and processes leading to their variability in natural and controlled atmospheres and integrates, harmonizes and distributes datasets, activities and services provided by Central Facilities and National Facilities.

ACTRIS data - the data produced by the ACTRIS National Facilities complying with the procedures established within ACTRIS and is defined in ACTRIS data policy as accepted and amended by the decisions of the Interim ACTRIS Council and later General Assembly.

ACTRIS ERIC - The Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure European Research Infrastructure Consortium is the legal entity that coordinates and facilitates the operation of ACTRIS at the European level, ensuring long-term sustainability, governance, and strategic development of the research infrastructure. ACTRIS ERIC includes all functions of ACTRIS Head Office and part of the Data Centre. The statutory seat of ACTRIS ERIC is in Helsinki, Finland.

ACTRIS label - The "ACTRIS National Facility" label is granted through the ACTRIS labelling process to Observational and Exploratory Platforms that comply with the ACTRIS standards.

ACTRIS labelling process - proves the operational capacities of the National Facilities and ensures the high quality of ACTRIS data by granting the label "ACTRIS National Facility" to Observational and Exploratory Platforms that comply with the ACTRIS standards.

ACTRIS observational components - ACTRIS observational components refer to the classification of measurement techniques. ACTRIS has six observational components: aerosol in situ (AIS), cloud in situ (CIS), reactive trace gases in situ (RTGIS), aerosol remote sensing (ARS), cloud remote sensing (CRS), and reactive trace gases remote sensing (RTGRS).

Atmospheric Simulation Chamber Committee (ASCC) - supports the operation of ACTRIS atmospheric simulation chambers on matters rela-

ted to procedures, quality, consistency and relevance.

Central Facility (CF) - a European-level ACTRIS component, either Head Office, Data Centre or Topical Centre, that offers ACTRIS data or research services and other services to users as well as operation support to National Facilities.

Central Facility (CF) Leader - the person responsible for leading, managing, developing and implementing the activities of a Central Facility according to the agreed ACTRIS policies and rules.

Central Facility (CF) Unit - part of a Central Facility located at and operated by a research performing organization (RPO) or by ACTRIS ERIC.

Central Facility (CF) Unit Head - the person responsible for the coordination and representation of a Central Facility Unit.

Central Facility (CF) Management Board - an internal Management Board to support the implementation of CF tasks and the daily CF operation and management. Each Central Facility (DC and TCs) has this board and it is chaired by the CF leader and includes the Head of each CF Unit.

Centre for Aerosol In Situ Measurements (CAIS-ECAC) - one of the six ACTRIS Topical Centres. The European Centre for Aerosol Calibration and Characterization (ECAC) acts as the ACTRIS Centre for Aerosol In Situ measurements (CAIS), whose mission is to offer operation support to ACTRIS National Facilities operating instrumentation for aerosol in situ measurements and specialized services to a wide range of users.

Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing (CARS) - one of the six ACTRIS Topical Centres. The mission of the CARS is to offer operation support to ACTRIS National Facilities operating aerosol remote sensing instrumentation and specialized services to a wide range of users.

Centre for Cloud In Situ Measurements (CIS) - one of the six ACTRIS Topical Centres. The mission of the CIS is to offer operational support to ACTRIS National Facilities operating instrumentation for

cloud in situ measurements and specialized services to wide range of users.

Centre for Cloud Remote Sensing (CCRES) – one of the six ACTRIS Topical Centres. The mission of the CCRES is to offer operational support to ACTRIS National Facilities operating cloud remote sensing instrumentation and specialized services to a wide range of users.

Centre for Reactive Trace Gases In Situ Measurements (CiGas) – One of the six ACTRIS Topical Centres. The mission of CiGas is to offer operational support to ACTRIS National Facilities operating instrumentation for reactive trace gases in situ measurements and specialized services to a wide range of users.

Centre for Reactive Trace Gases Remote Sensing (CREGARS) – One of the six ACTRIS Topical Centres. The mission of CREGARS is to offer operational support to ACTRIS National Facilities operating reactive trace gases remote sensing instrumentation and specialized services to a wide range of users.

Cooperation Agreement – an agreement between ACTRIS ERIC and a National Facility or between ACTRIS ERIC and a Central Facility which is not included in ACTRIS ERIC.

Data Centre (DC) – the Central Facility responsible for ACTRIS data curation, preservation, and distribution of the data, value-added products and tools, and hosting the ACTRIS data portal that is a single-entry point for all ACTRIS data.

Director General (DG) – the legal representative of ACTRIS ERIC appointed by the General Assembly; responsible for the implementation of the decisions by the General Assembly and ensure the scientific and strategic development of ACTRIS.

Ethical Advisory Board – consists of independent external members appointed by the General Assembly; the board provides feedback and makes recommendations to develop the ethical aspects of ACTRIS ERIC and the research infrastructure activities.

Exploratory Platform – ACTRIS National Facility; an atmospheric simulation chamber, a laboratory or a mobile platform that performs dedicated experiments and provides quality-controlled data on atmospheric compounds, processes, events or regions of relevance by following common standards.

Financial Committee – consists of expert members appointed by the General Assembly; the committee supports on matters related to the management of financial planning of ACTRIS ERIC as an advisory body of GA.

General Assembly (GA) – the governing body of ACTRIS ERIC, composed of delegates of members, permanent observers and observers.

Head Office (HO) – the Central Facility responsible for coordinating and representing ACTRIS as well as enabling ACTRIS services. HO supports the work of the General Assembly, the advisory bodies and committees of the ACTRIS ERIC.

Host country – a country where a Central Facility unit is located and operated.

Host contribution – support provided by members or permanent observers for the functioning of the Central Facilities that are not part of ACTRIS ERIC, hosted in their own country.

Host premium contribution – the support provided by ACTRIS ERIC members and permanent observers for the functioning of the Central Facilities that are part of ACTRIS ERIC, hosted in their own country.

In situ measurements – in the context of ACTRIS, in situ measurements of aerosol, cloud, and reactive-trace-gas properties refer to techniques that characterise a sampling point. They can be performed from Observational Platform near the surface, from mobile surface-based or airborne platforms, and in atmospheric simulation chambers and laboratories. ACTRIS has three in situ observational components (AIS, CIS, RTGIS).

ACTRIS Scientific Advisor – an expert appointed by the Director General to advise ACTRIS on scientific matters, supporting the development and advancement of ACTRIS research and services.

Member of ACTRIS ERIC – a Member State of the European Union, associated country, third country other than associated country, or an intergovernmental organization that has joined ACTRIS ERIC. The rules of ACTRIS membership and obligations and rights of members are defined in the ACTRIS ERIC statutes.

Membership contribution – a cash contribution to ACTRIS ERIC to be collected from a member, permanent observer or observer according to the rules defined in the ACTRIS Internal Financial Rules.

ACTRIS ERIC is responsible for allocating the agreed contributions to each Central Facility.

National Contact Person (NCP) – a person nominated by the countries that have shown their commitment to ACTRIS at organizational or state level. The ACTRIS National Contact Person is responsible for organizing the coordination of the ACTRIS community at the national level and is responsible for ensuring the proper dissemination and information flow from the European ACTRIS activities to the national science communities and the relevant national stakeholders.

National Facility (NF) – an observational or exploratory platform which has a contractual relationship with ACTRIS ERIC and which provides data and/or physical/remote access to its premises. National Facilities are developed, managed and operated by national Research Performing Organisations.

National Facility Principal Investigator (NF PI) – The scientist in charge of the measurements performed at a National Facility, usually also the contact person of the facility.

National Facility (NF) Technical and Scientific Forum – a highly technical and operative forum to develop the RI and ensure the connection of scientific expertise and technological development. It is an advisory body that may provide recommendations to the RI Committee or to the ACTRIS community. The forum is inclusive; the forum is open for the whole ACTRIS community and ACTRIS users.

Observational Platform – ACTRIS National Facility; a fixed ground-based station acquiring reliable high-quality data on the variability of aerosol, clouds and trace gases and their complex interactions by applying standardized remote-sensing and in situ measurement techniques. Observational Platforms may also provide physical and/or remote access to users.

Observer of ACTRIS ERIC – a Member State of the European Union, associated country, third country other than associated country, or an intergovernmental organisation that has joined ACTRIS ERIC as an observer or permanent observer. The rules of ACTRIS observership and obligations and rights of observers are defined in the ACTRIS ERIC statutes.

Physical access – physical access to an ACTRIS Central Facility or National Facility. Centrally managed

via the ACTRIS Head Office's Service and Access Management Unit, following the ACTRIS Access and Service Policy.

Remote access – access to an ACTRIS Central Facility or National Facility without users physically visiting the facility.

Remote sensing measurements – in the context of ACTRIS, remote sensing measurements refer to active and passive atmospheric remote-sensing techniques for the observation of aerosol, clouds, and trace gases. They can be applied at observational sites and on mobile surfacebased platforms. ACTRIS has three remote sensing observational components (ARS, CRS, RTGRS).

Research Infrastructure Committee (RI Committee) – the committee supports the Director General on matters related to the Research Infrastructure to ensure consistency, coherence, and sustainability of the operations of the Research Infrastructure. The RI Committee is convened by the Director General and shall have representatives both from the Central Facilities and National Facilities.

Scientific and Innovation Advisory Board (SIAB) – consists of independent external members appointed by the General Assembly; the board monitors the scientific and operative quality of ACTRIS and advises on development of ACTRIS ERIC and the research infrastructure activities in the operation phase.

Science and User Access Forum – a focused space dedicated to all matters related to the physical and remote access of users to ACTRIS services and for users to interact with ACTRIS.

Service and Access Management Unit (SAMU) – a Unit of ACTRIS Head Office facilitating the access to ACTRIS services.

Topical Centre (TC) – a Central Facility supporting the operation of the National Facilities and offering services and operation support for quality assurance and quality control of ACTRIS measurements and data (including training and knowledge transfer, calibration, quality assurance/quality control tools, and development of standard operation and evaluation procedures).

Six Topical Centres are set up to respond to the scientific and technical needs of ACTRIS, each with a particular focus on either remote sensing (from the ground) or in situ (near-surface) measurements:

- **CAIS-ECAC** – Centre for Aerosol In Situ Measurements – European Centre for Aerosol Calibration and Characterization
- **CARS** – Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing
- **CIS** – Centre for Cloud In Situ Measurements
- **CCRES** – Centre for Cloud Remote Sensing
- **CiGas** – Centre for Reactive Trace Gases In Situ Measurements
- **CREGARS** – Centre for Reactive Trace Gases Remote Sensing

User – a person, a team, or an institution making use of ACTRIS data or other ACTRIS services, including access to ACTRIS facilities.

Virtual access – wide and free access to ACTRIS data and digital tools provided by DC through the ACTRIS website.

ACTRIS data and service specific glossary

ACTRIS data levels

- **level 0 data:** Raw sensor output. Native resolution, metadata necessary for next level.
- **level 1 data:** Calibrated and quality assured data with minimum level of quality control.
- **level 2 data:** Approved and fully quality controlled ACTRIS data product or geophysical variable.
- **level 3 data:** Elaborated ACTRIS data products derived by post-processing of ACTRIS Level 0 -1 -2 data, and data from other sources. The data can be gridded or not.

Data curation – the activity that stores, manages and ensures access to all persistent data sets produced within the infrastructure.

Data originator – entity operating instruments at a National Facility or Topical Centre, resulting in ACTRIS data and delivering ACTRIS data to the Data Centre.

Data provider – the Data Centre offering the ACTRIS data and value-added data products and tools to users.

Digital tools – tailored codes and software for processing and visualization of ACTRIS data, production of ACTRIS data products, and for data analysis and research.

Data traceability – an unbroken chain of uniquely identified process steps leading from raw data to any kind of processed data, where identification of process steps follows the data.

Measurement traceability – an unbroken chain of comparisons relating an instrument's measurements to a known standard, in the ideal case SI units.

Quality assurance and control – quality assurance is process-oriented and focuses on defect prevention and quality control is product-oriented and focuses on defect identification:

- **Quality Assurance (QA)** – the process or set of processes used to ensure the quality of a product (e.g. data series, instrument, sample, measured value of a variable, etc.).
 - **Quality Control (QC)** – the process and activities of ensuring products and services meet the expectations.
-

Synthesis product – data product not under direct ACTRIS responsibility from e.g. research activities, citizen science, for which ACTRIS offers repository and access.

Variables – almost 135 different atmospheric variables are measured within ACTRIS. The variables are listed in the ACTRIS data management plan.

Delegates of the ACTRIS General Assembly

Country	Name	Affiliation
Austria	Karolina Begusch-Pfefferkorn	Federal Ministry of Education, Science and Research of Austria
Belgium	Aline van der Werf	Belgian Science Policy Office
Bulgaria	Kalin Mutavchiev	Ministry of Education and Science of Bulgaria
Bulgaria	Tanja Dreischuh	Institute of Electronics – Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
Czech Republic	Zdimal Vladimir	Institute of Chemical Process Fundamentals of the CAS
Czech Republic	Jiri Svehla	The Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports
Cyprus	Michalis Mouskos	Department of Meteorology Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment
Cyprus	Charalambos Papatryfonos	Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digital Policy
Denmark	Mads Rugaard Christensen	The Ministry of Higher Education and Science
Finland	Petteri Kauppinen	Research Council of Finland
Finland	Hannele Korhonen	Finnish Meteorological Institute
France	Jean Marie Flaud	Ministry for Higher Education, Research and Innovation France
France	Jérôme Rose	French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS)
Germany	Jonas Esche	German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMU)

Germany	Jochen Elberskirch	DLR Projektträger
Italy	Mauro Bertelletti	Ministry of Education, Universities and Research
Italy	Gelsomina Pappalardo	National Research Council
Netherlands	Arnoud Apituley	Royal Netherlands Meteorological Institute (KNMI)
Norway	Odd Ivar Eriksen	The Research Council of Norway
Poland	Michał Rybiński	Ministry of Science and Higher Education
Poland	Iwona Stachlewska	Institute of Geophysics, Faculty of Physics, University of Warsaw
Romania	Viorel Vulturescu	Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitalization
Romania	Beatrice Păduroiu	Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitalization
Spain	María Vallejo Abascal	The Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities
Sweden	Sara Moa	Swedish Research Council
Sweden	Ulf Jonsell	Swedish Research Council
Switzerland	Maarten Lupker	State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation SERI

Members of the ACTRIS Scientific and Innovation Advisory Board

Name	Affiliation and Title
Leonard Barrie	Prof. Emeritus Stockholm University and The Cyprus Institute, Adjunct Prof. McGill University, Montreal, Chair of the SIAB
Øystein Hov	Secretary General, The Norwegian Academy of Science and Letters
Vincent-Henri Peuch	Head of Site for European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), Director for engagement with the EU
Carlo Rizzuto	Prof., Chair of the General Assembly, CERIC-ERIC (Central European Research Infrastructure Consortium), 3rd chair of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)
Valérie Thouret	Co-Coordinator of the European Research Infrastructure In-service Aircraft for Global Observing System (IAGOS-AISBL)
Paolo Laj	Head, Atmospheric Environment Research, World Meteorological Organization (WMO), Head of the Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW) Programme of WMO

The EU Projects of ACTRIS ERIC in 2025

Name of the project	Description of the project	Logo
<p>ATMO-ACCESS</p> <p>2021-2025</p> <p>Read more</p>	<p>The EU Horizon 2020 project “Solutions for Sustainable Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities” (ATMO-ACCESS) is the organised response of distributed atmospheric research facilities for developing a pilot for a new model of Integrating Activities.</p>	
<p>RI-URBANS</p> <p>2021-2025</p> <p>Read more</p>	<p>The “Research Infrastructures Reinforcing Air Quality Monitoring Capacities in European Urban & Industrial AreaS” is a EU Horizon 2020 project that develops and integrates advanced air quality monitoring systems for improving urban air quality.</p>	
<p>ENVRINNOV</p> <p>2024-2027</p> <p>Read more</p>	<p>Funded under the EU Horizon Europe, the ENVRINNOV project fosters innovation within environmental research infrastructures by developing a centralized platform to enhance technology transfer, industry collaboration, and service uptake.</p>	
<p>IRISCC</p> <p>2024-2028</p> <p>Read more</p>	<p>The “Integrated Research Infrastructure Services for Climate Change Risks” scientific and knowledge services to foster cutting-edge research and evidence-based policymaking to improve Europe’s resilience to climate change.</p>	
<p>POLARIN</p> <p>2024-2029</p> <p>Read more</p>	<p>POLARIN is an international network of polar research infrastructures and their services, aiming at addressing the scientific challenges of the polar regions.</p>	
<p>CARGO-ACT</p> <p>2024-2027</p> <p>Read more</p>	<p>The goal of the EU HORIZON CARGO-ACT project is to deliver a clear roadmap for sustainable global cooperation between key organisations in Europe and in the United States to provide the best possible services for accessing and using information from monitoring climate- and air quality-relevant properties of aerosol, cloud and trace gases in the atmosphere.</p>	

Exploring the Atmosphere

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